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Deliverable

1.3	D11	Best practice guidelines for PBM upscaling for industrial applications
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Executive Summary

This report provides guidelines for industrial application of population balance modelling (PBM), in so far as it is relevant to the TUSAIL International Training Network (ITN), Work Package 1 (WP1).

The main research goal of TUSAIL (Training in Upscaling Particle Systems: Advancing Industry across Length-scale) is to establish physics-based modelling to predict the behaviour of large industrial unit operations and processes via reliable upscaling methodologies and tools. In TUSAIL, three complementary upscaling approaches will be developed based on (i) population balance modelling (PBM), (ii) coarse-grained meso-particle methods, and (iii) coupling between discrete and continuum methods.

TUSAIL WP1 is the responsible work package for the first upscaling approach and the report has been structured in a way to highlight the PBM approach applied for a few unit operations where solid particulate systems are of focus. The unit operations such as mixing, transport and discharge can be part of PBM within a flowsheet simulation, but are not unit operations (UO's) that influence particle properties such as particle size. Therefore, they are not discussed in this report. After introducing the fundamentals of PBM, DEM and CFD-DEM coupling, in previous reports this report focuses on guidelines for application examples (UO's) where PBM is used.

Although PBM has been an area of interest in research for quite some time, still more effort is needed to develop the models and kernels that enable us to predict the behaviour of industrial-scale particulate systems accurately and with low computational effort. Therefore, a number of challenges and open questions need to be addressed, dealt and answered, a few of which are mentioned in chapters of this report. TUSAIL aims to deliver solutions to some of the existing challenges.

At the point of writing this report, the authors (ESRs) are working on the implementation of the mechanistic models (PBM) for their respective systems of interest and have preliminary information and results on the application of PBM within their work. The authors (ESRs) intend to couple CFD-DEM to PBM (either implicitly i.e., within the simulation run or explicitly i.e, in a post-processing sense) and investigate the influence of particle level phenomena, then try to upscale towards the process level. The strategies are elaborated in chapters that follow.

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Chapter 1

Purpose of the report

This report represents the third deliverable of Work Package-1 (WP-1) in the TUSAIL-ITN. WP-1 aims to use predictive modeling methods like population balance modeling (PBM) to track the morphological changes of particles due to the physical phenomena (like agglomeration and breakage). The subjects covered in the chapters and parts that follow absolutely fall inside the subject of the WP-1 ESRs. Each chapter represents an application example of the actual process, which is a key component of the process engineering industry. The emphasis is on the description of the modeling approaches, preliminary results, and the resulting best practice guidelines for each project, are outlined in the chapters to follow.

Organization of the report

- Chapter 2 describes the development of surrogate models for PBM. The application is agglomeration in fluidized beds. The models are derived from lab scale experiments and CFD-DEM simulations. The experimental and numerical setups are described and the development of surrogate models explained. The best practice guidelines for industrial application are discussed.
- Chapter 3 describes the implementation details of a CFD-DEM-PBM framework specific for particle breakage in granular systems, especially jet mills. The chapter provides a concise overview of various methods available for characterizing breakage, ultimately detailing the method chosen by the author for implementation. Furthermore, it offers a practical demonstration of the implemented PBM module's utility, showcasing its application towards enhancing design efficiency. A curated list of best practices is also provided based on the author's experiences in the domain of particle comminution using fluidized-bed opposed jet mills.

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- Chapter 4 describes the modeling framework, considerations and assumptions for the particle breakage in wet-operated stirred media mills using coupled CFD-DEM and PBM approaches. The details include motivation for the modeling approach, overview of model considerations, and simulation setup. The sections 4.5, and 4.7 indicate the upcoming tasks in the project and the best practice guidelines to model the wet stirred media mills, respectively.

Chapter 2

DEM derived surrogate modelling in PBM applied to fluidized bed agglomeration

2.1 Introduction

Particle processing techniques like fluidized bed agglomeration are widely employed in many industries and offer a versatile means of producing particles with certain properties. Agglomeration and granulation using fluidized bed spray technology are crucial procedures in the food, fine chemical and pharmaceutical sectors. Fluidized bed agglomeration maximizes heat and mass transfer and makes it possible to produce powders that are dust-free and flow easily, which is crucial for the food sector (Heinrich et al., 2003; B. Wang et al., 2021; Yuksel and Dirim, 2018). In the pharmaceutical manufacturing process, agglomeration is also frequently employed for a number of essential objectives, such as: (i) improving the powders' flowability, porosity and homogeneity, (ii) avoiding segregation, (iii) controlling the rate of drug release and (iv) reducing dust production (Shanmugam, 2017). The procedure modifies the size of the final product and eliminates surplus moisture from the particle, strengthening it for subsequent processing—like tableting, which is mostly applicable in the pharmaceutical sector—by increasing its strength (Ouazzou et al., 2023).

Numerous variables that also impact the fluid bed agglomeration process itself might have an impact on the final product's size and structure (Avilés-Avilés et al., 2015; Rambali et al., 2001). Agglomeration is the general process of binding primary particles together to form larger, porous secondary particles called agglomerates. The following physical processes are linked to a fluid bed granulator: (i) liquid atomization into fine droplets, (ii) droplet evaporation, (iii) droplet deposition onto particle surfaces, (iv) drying of the particles and (v) formation of agglomerates

from wet particles. Heat and mass transfer in a fluidized bed are highly correlated and the many interrelated processes happen simultaneously (Askarishahi et al., 2017, 2019; Terrazas-Velarde et al., 2011).

Historically, the use of CFD-DEM simulations has been crucial in comprehending the behaviour of particles in fluidized beds (Askarishahi et al., 2017; Atxutegi et al., 2023; Diez et al., 2019; Dosta et al., 2010; Fries et al., 2011; Fries et al., 2013; Kieckhefen et al., 2018, 2020; Pietsch et al., 2019; Pietsch et al., 2018; Wu et al., 2018). Nevertheless, these simulations can be demanding in terms of computational resources, particularly when handling extensive industrial applications. This requires the development of more effective modeling techniques that can offer precise forecasts while minimizing processing requirements. DEM provides a comprehensive depiction of the interactions between individual particles, rendering it a key tool for investigating the dynamics of particle flow and particle properties (Ouazzou et al., 2023; Tausendschön and Radl, 2021; Tausendschön et al., 2023; Zheng et al., 2021). It enables the examination of particle motion and collision dynamics, which are essential for comprehending agglomeration phenomena. DEM properly depicts the behavior of individual particles, it is unable to represent the effects of those particles on large-scale process changes (Barrasso and Ramachandran, 2016; Peng et al., 2010). It is evident that although both modeling approaches are important for particle processes, none of them is capable of predicting the results of totally different particulate processes at different scales on its own. PBM is effective in predicting macroscopic behaviour but it is also limited in integrating many system factors and is dependent on fitting values of unknown parameters (Ding et al., 2006; Hussain et al., 2013).

PBM offers a structure for depicting the size distribution and the rate of alteration in the population of particles caused by different processes, such as agglomeration. These factors make it interesting to combine the two methods DEM and PBM in order to predict and model various kinds of particle processes. With the help of precise information from DEM about system insights (particle velocity, collision frequency, etc.) PBM kernels can be formulated to anticipate new particle distributions. Studies that combine DEM and PBM methodologies can be found in the literature. In some studies, (Gantt et al., 2006; Reinhold and Briesen, 2012) collision data was extracted from DEM simulations and a coalescence kernel using one-way coupling developed. (Dosta and Chan, 2022) recently examined the mechanical behavior of agglomerates in a uni-axial compression setup using a one-way DEM-ANN-PBM coupling approach. A pseudo-coupled DEM-PBM approach was employed by (Capece et al., 2018) to model breakage mechanisms. Various techniques for bi-directional coupling have been developed to model various particle processes (Barrasso and Ramachandran, 2015; Barrasso et al., 2014; Sen and Ramachandran, 2013; Sen et al., 2014; Tamrakar and Ramachandran, 2019). Periodically implementing the PBM inside DEM was successfully done by (Barrasso and Ramachandran, 2015; Barrasso et al., 2014; Sen et al., 2014). Two-way coupling model was effectively employed by several authors (Baba

et al., 2021; Barrasso and Ramachandran, 2015, 2016), whose authors primarily used the PBM to save computational costs and only occasionally utilized the DEM.

Integrating DEM and PBM in a unified framework is challenging because of the differences in scales, complexity and computational demand. To address these difficulties, this study presents sophisticated modeling methods that utilize CFD-DEM simulations to guide the development of surrogate models and innovative agglomeration kernels. These models seek to accurately represent the fundamental dynamics of particle wetting, velocity and collision frequency, which are crucial components in the process of agglomeration.

Additionally, there is a need for more comprehensive agglomeration kernels that can precisely depict the intricate physics of particle interactions, in addition to the advancement of these surrogate models. This study presents a new agglomeration kernel that includes mechanistic surrogate models derived from experiments and CFD-DEM simulations. The purpose of this integration is to offer a more advanced and systematic tool for modeling agglomeration processes, surpassing the constraints of current empirical models and presenting a possible substitute to direct simulations for process optimization.

This study aims to highlight the crucial role of advanced modeling techniques in enhancing our understanding and control of particle agglomeration processes. It establishes the basis for simpler and proficient design and optimization of fluidized bed agglomerators. Advancing from empirical methods to mechanistic approaches enables enhanced comprehension of processes, leading to improved predictability across various scales.

2.2 Methodology

2.2.1 Material

The study utilizes maltodextrin, a complex carbohydrate derived from the partial enzymatic degradation of potato starch. The chosen type of maltodextrin possesses a dextrose concentration of around 20 weight percent. The food-grade maltodextrin is marketed under the product name Avebe MD20P by Biesterfeld AG in Germany.

Maltodextrin, being a polysaccharide, consists of a chain of glucose molecules linked together by glycosidic bonds. The dextrose content, measured at 18.9 *w%*, indicates the ratio of glucose within the maltodextrin. The choice of this mixture was made based on its exceptional solubility and functional properties. Consequently, it is frequently employed as a model substance in the food sector. Maltodextrin undergoes careful processing to ensure the prevention of contamination and to ensure the preservation of its inherent stability. The material was preserved in a regulated environment, taking into account temperature and humidity, to ensure its structural stability

until it was used in experiments. To minimize the variability in the experiment's outcomes, maltodextrin sourced from a single producer and batch was consistently employed throughout the whole trial. This ensures the capacity to reproduce outcomes and minimizes the potential for any extraneous variables that may occur due to variations in material characteristics. The meticulous and comprehensive selection and characterization of maltodextrin exemplify the commitment to precision in the methodologies of this study, laying the foundation for reliable and meaningful results.

The particle size of the powder has been accurately determined using the dynamic image analyzer Camsizer XT (Microtrac Retsch GmbH, Germany) yielding the following key measurements: the particles have a d_{10} of 40 μm , the d_{50} is 140 μm and the d_{90} is 230 μm . The powder's moisture level remains consistently at approximately 3 weight percent throughout storage.

Prior to conducting agglomeration trials, the maltodextrin powder undergoes sieving. This stage is crucial for removing small particles that can easily adhere to filters and surfaces due to elutriation. While it is feasible to agglomerate these fine particles, they are typically discarded in industrial settings through the process of sieving. The maltodextrin powder after sieved exhibits the following particle size distribution: the d_{10} , d_{50} and d_{90} are 70 μm , 160 μm and 260 μm , respectively. Figure 2.1 illustrates the PSD. Following the agglomeration process, which lasts a few minutes, substantial increases in particle size are seen. Specifically, the diameter d_{10} increases to an average of 220 μm , d_{50} increases to 440 μm and d_{90} increases to 840 μm over a period of 15 minutes. The observed growth indicates that, on average, particles experience a threefold enlargement in size throughout all investigations within a 15-minute period. Moreover, it is essential to recognize that the porosity of the particles undergoes modification during the agglomeration process. The likely reason for this is the formation of voids between the primary particles inside an agglomerate.

2.2.1.1 Lab scale fluidized bed

The fluidized bed utilized in this investigation is the GF3 laboratory-scale fluidized bed manufactured by Glatt GmbH, Germany. Figure 2.2 illustrates a schematic drawing of the conical fluidized bed configuration featuring internal filters. The air distributor plate has a diameter of 18 cm and is equipped with a mesh size of 105 μm . The fluidized bed operates in a top spray mode with a nozzle air pressure of 2 abar and an air volume flow rate of 2 m^3/h . The nozzle configuration comprises a Series 970-S4 (manufactured by Düsen-Schlick GmbH, Germany) with a liquid nozzle orifice diameter of 1.2 mm. The air cap at level 3 is used, resulting in a spray angle of approximately 50°. The spray setting produces droplets with a d_{50} of 33 μm . The spray characteristics utilized can be located in (Kramm et al., 2023) and other sources for various spray setups. The spray nozzle is positioned at a vertical distance of 25 cm from the distributor plate.

FIGURE 2.1: Particle size distribution of initial material after sieving.

The aqueous solution is transferred into the chamber using a TBE peristaltic pump manufactured by MDX Biotechnik International GmbH, Germany. The experiments are conducted using a batch process, with a bed mass of 0.5 kg.

FIGURE 2.2: Scheme of the lab scale fluidized bed setup.

The filters are cleansed by reversing the flow direction through each individual filter for a duration of 1 second at a pressure of 4 bar. The filter cleaning operation is conducted at a frequency of

once per minute and normally has a duration of approximately 30 seconds. Once the filters have been cleaned, samples are gathered. Consequently, the intervals at which the sample drawings occur are a multiple of the complete cleaning cycle, which has a total duration of around 1.5 minutes. The samples for offline measurements are extracted from the sample drawer, positioned at a bed height of 16 cm and a radial depth of 2 cm.

A precision balance is utilized to accurately measure the moisture content of granules in offline samples weighing around 1 gram. Prior to and subsequent to the drying process, the samples undergo a process of being assigned a weight. The moisture content can be calculated using equation 2.1. The specimens are dehydrated in the oven for a duration of 5 days at a temperature of 110 °C. The samples are dispersed throughout the container to form a thin layer, so expediting the drying process. The approach is being compared to a well-established infrared moisture analyzer. The data align with the moisture analyzer EM 120-HR manufactured by Precisa Gravimetrics AG in Germany.

$$MC = \frac{m_{wet} - m_{dry}}{m_{wet}} * 100 \quad (2.1)$$

2.2.1.2 Porosimetry

The material is milled to a fine powder and then its skeletal density is measured using the AccuPyc 1330 helium pycnometer from Micromeritics Instrument Corporation, United States. The measured skeletal density shown in equation 2.2 is 1480 kg/m^3 similar to the literature values Kammerhofer et al., 2019 and Descamps et al., 2013.

$$\rho_s = \frac{m_s}{V_s} \quad (2.2)$$

The initial powder's poured bulk density shown in equation 2.3 was measured to be 564 kg/m^3 similar to values in literature Descamps et al., 2013.

$$\rho_{bulk} = \frac{m_s}{V_{bulk}} \quad (2.3)$$

The tap density shown in equation 2.4 is measured according to ISO 787-11. The material is dried in an oven before measurement at 110 °C for multiple days until dry. The tap density is measured in a suitable measuring cylinder. The cylinder is placed on a rotating 3D printed camshaft, using Ultimaker 3 (Ultimaker B.V., Netherlands), which is designed according to ISO 787-11. The material is tapped for 5 minutes at 250 rpm totalling 1250 revolutions.

$$\rho_{tap} = \frac{m_s}{V_{tap}} \quad (2.4)$$

2.2.2 Design of experiment

In order to construct a DoE, it is necessary to identify the critical process factors that determine whether a product may still be acquired following the experiment. To carry out the experimental study, a two-phase full factorial design was chosen, resulting in the development of an extended full factorial design that incorporates a center point (Vanaret et al., 2021). The experimental technique involves manipulating several factors, namely the volume flow rate of air used for fluidization, the temperature of the inlet air and the rate at which liquid is sprayed. These parameters are listed in table 2.1.

TABLE 2.1: Process parameters used in lab-scale batch agglomeration experiments.

Inlet air flow rate [m^3/h]	Inlet air temperature [$^{\circ}C$]	Spray rate [g/min]
60	40	6
75	60	10
80	70	12
85	80	14
100	100	18

Due to defluidization, samples and experiments had to be excluded from the dataset. This resulted in an uneven distribution of moisture and inconsistent readings. In the event of a significant standard deviation caused by measurement mistakes or rapid agglomeration resulting in a heterogeneously dispersed bed, samples and experiments are removed. Additionally, samples are extracted to address defluidization, resulting in an uneven distribution. The final dataset consists of 29 experiments and 169 samples.

2.2.3 PBM

Population balance modeling provides an extensive approach for understanding and predicting the development of particle characteristics in a system as time advances. PBMs can model complex mechanisms essential to designing, optimizing and scaling up industrial processes by

accounting for nucleation, layering, agglomeration, breakage and consolidation. This chapter presents the theoretical basis of PBM and explains its mathematical representation.

The fundamental concept of PBM involves representing the distribution of particle features (such as size, shape, composition) in a distribution, while considering how these qualities vary over time due to particular mechanisms. The balance equation is based on the notion of conserving the number or volume of particles, which represents the overall impact of every mechanism influencing the population.

Equation 2.5 in the study of Kumar et al., 2013 demonstrates the general Population Balance Equation (PBE) incorporating agglomeration. The agglomeration terms are displayed on the right side. Equation 2.6 represents the birth term, while equation 2.7 represents the death term together they characterize agglomeration.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} n(x, t) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[n \frac{dx}{dt} \right] (x, t) = B_{\text{agg}}(x, t) - D_{\text{agg}}(x, t) \quad (2.5)$$

The birth term is multiplied by a prefactor of 1/2 to reflect the fact that two primary particles merge to create a single particle. This prevents the presence of an inaccurate number of particles in the PSD's bins.

$$B_{\text{agg}}(x) = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^x \beta(x-y, y) n(x-y, t) n(y, t) dy \quad (2.6)$$

$$D_{\text{agg}}(x) = n(x, t) \int_0^\infty \beta(x, y) n(y, t) dy \quad (2.7)$$

To derive the integro-partial differential equation 2.8, equations 2.5, 2.6 and 2.7 are combined.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} n(x, t) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[n \frac{dx}{dt} \right] (x, t) &= \frac{1}{2} \int_0^x \beta(x-y, y) n(x-y, t) n(y, t) dy \\ &\quad - n(x, t) \int_0^\infty \beta(x, y) n(y, t) dy \end{aligned} \quad (2.8)$$

An in depth description of theory and applications of PBM is given in Ramkrishna and Singh, 2014.

2.2.3.1 Setup

All PBM simulations are executed using gProms (Siemens). The internal gProms DAEBDF solver (Oh and Pantelides, 1996; Vassiliadis et al., 1994a, 1994b) was utilized with the default settings. The numerical settings together with the initial conditions and process parameters can be found in table 2.2. The initial particle size distribution is a logarithmic distribution. PSD, temperature and moisture content of the material in the chamber is preset to values from the first sample of experiments. This is also the start of the liquid spray. The absolute humidity of the inlet air is similar for all experiments. The PSD is tracked on a grid of 10 size classes.

TABLE 2.2: Numerical settings, initial conditions and process parameters. “Ind” refers to the individual settings of each experiment.

Parameter	Unit	Value
Numerics		
Minimum particle size	μm	50
Maximum particle size	μm	1000
Number of size classes	-	10
Initial conditions		
Total mass	kg	0.514
Mass fraction wet air	w%	2.9
Mass fraction granule	w%	97.1
Temperature	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	Ind
Initial conditions: Solid		
Bulk density	kg/m^3	580
Mass fraction liquid	w%	Ind
Mass fraction solid	w%	Ind
Median size	μm	Ind
Standard deviation	μm	Ind
Initial conditions: Vapour		
Absolute humidity	g/kg	7.8

TABLE 2.2: Numerical settings, initial conditions and process parameters. “Ind” refers to the individual settings of each experiment.

Parameter	Unit	Value
Process parameters		
Vapour flow rate	m^3/h	Ind
Vapour temperature	$^{\circ}C$	Ind
Spray liquid flow rate	g/min	Ind
Spray liquid temperature	$^{\circ}C$	18

The equipment parameters of the granulator and the drying model properties are shown in table 2.3. The heat loss is calculated with a fitted constant heat transfer coefficient and equation 2.9.

$$Q_{loss} = kA(T_{internal} - T_{environment}) \quad (2.9)$$

Liquid addition to the system is simplified, therefore liquid is not atomized and droplets do not dry before collision with particles. The liquid is distributed independent of size which leads to an equal distribution of liquid as a default. The improved particle wetting is described in chapter 2.2.5.2. The drying model used in the simulations is from Burgschweiger and Tsotsas, 2002. The drying curve is a linear single particle drying curve. The mass transfer coefficient is calculated according to Burgschweiger and Tsotsas, 2002. The sorption isotherm is modelled with the BET model Brunauer et al., 1938. The critical moisture content is used as a fitting parameter.

TABLE 2.3: Equipment specifications and drying model parameters.

Parameter	Unit	Value
Equipment		
Bed cross sectional area	m^2	0.025
Ambient temp	$^{\circ}C$	23
Wall heat transfer coefficient	$W/m^2/^{\circ}C$	20
Wall surface area	m^2	0.193
Equipment volume	m^3	0.012

TABLE 2.3: Equipment specifications and drying model parameters.

Parameter	Unit	Value
Drying		
Critical moisture content	kg/kg_{dry}	0.43
Bulk Sherwood correction	-	1

The material specifications for solid, liquid and gas phase are shown in table 2.4.

TABLE 2.4: Material specifications for solid, liquid and gas.

Parameter	Unit	Value
Solid		
Skeletal density	kg/m^3	1525
Specific heat capacity	J/kg/K	1220
Liquid		
Density	kg/m^3	1000
Specific heat capacity	J/kg/K	4180
Dynamic viscosity	Pa s	1E-03
Vapour		
Diffusivity	m^2/s	2E-05
Thermal conductivity	W/m/K	2.4E-02

The agglomeration settings when using the kernel by Rajniak et al., 2009 are as shown in table 2.5. The parameters used for maltodextrin in this study are the similar as the study found for lactose since it has similar wetting behaviour and properties. Physical parameter f deviates from lactose using 5 instead of 29.8 for maltodextrin. The other parameters remain the same

TABLE 2.5: Agglomeration parameters for Rajniak et al., 2009 kernel.

Parameter	Unit	Value
Collision rate constant	ln(1/s)	-3.4
Particle collision velocity	m/s	0.1
Gyration radius	µm	60
Physical parameter b	-	33
Physical parameter c	-	0.2
Physical parameter f	-	5
Physical parameter g	-	0.4

2.2.3.2 Binder agglomeration kernel

This chapter describes the approach used to create the new agglomeration kernel, which incorporates features from existing kernels. It includes the mathematical derivation of the kernel, along with the assumptions that were made and how the kernel was integrated into the PBM framework. The resulting kernel is shown in equation 2.10.

$$\beta(v, u) = \beta_0 \psi_{l,\lambda} (l + \lambda)^2 \sqrt{\frac{1}{l^3} + \frac{1}{\lambda^3}} \quad (2.10)$$

Hounslow described an aggregation kernel known as the equipartition of kinetic energy (EKE model) (Hounslow, 1998) is shown in equation 2.11. This model implies that particles collide because of their random velocity component and that this randomness leads to an equal distribution of the particles' kinetic energy.

$$\beta(v, u) = \beta_0 (l + \lambda)^2 \sqrt{\frac{1}{l^3} + \frac{1}{\lambda^3}} \quad (2.11)$$

A strong foundation for capturing the success of particle interactions is provided by Rajniak's kernel, which is well-known for its empirical approach to simulating particle agglomeration in fluidized beds (Rajniak et al., 2009). The success factor determines whether a collision leads to agglomeration or not. The success factor as determined by (Rajniak et al., 2009) consist of a geometric and a physical success factor shown in equation 2.12.

$$\psi_{l,\lambda} = \psi_{l,\lambda}^{geom} \psi_{l,\lambda}^{phys} \quad (2.12)$$

The geometric success factor determines the probability that two colliding particles get in contact on a wet spot (Goldschmidt, 2001). The accessible binder fraction is defined as relative frequency at which particles hit wet spot on a colliding particle from a random angle (Štěpánek et al., 2009).

$$\psi_{l,\lambda}^{geom} = 1 - (1 - \eta_l)(1 - \eta_\lambda) \quad (2.13)$$

The development of wet agglomerates was studied through simulations. The focus was on four regularly used pharmaceutical excipients and aimed to determine the relationship between the volumetric composition of a granule and the accessible binder fraction (Štěpánek et al., 2009). The simulation data points can be accurately represented by a sigmoidal function of the given form 2.14.

$$\eta = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-b(x-c)}} \quad (2.14)$$

The physical success factor can be determined by using the Stokes number analysis to non-deformable particles (Adetayo and Ennis, 1997; Ennis et al., 1991; Rajniak et al., 2007) and by extending this analysis to include deformable particles (Liu et al., 2000). Considering "Type-I" and "Type-II" coalescence of non-deformable particles results in the physical success factor as shown in equation 2.15.

$$\psi_{l,\lambda}^{phys} = \begin{cases} 1, & St \leq St^* \\ 0, & St > St^* \end{cases} \quad (2.15)$$

The stokes number is calculated as shown in equation 2.16.

$$St = \frac{8\tilde{m}u_0}{3\pi\mu\tilde{d}^2} \quad (2.16)$$

The critical Stokes number is shown in equation 2.17. h_a refers to the surface asperity height. The particle collision velocity u_0 is extracted from CFD-DEM simulations.

$$St^* = 2\ln\left(\frac{h}{h_a}\right) \quad (2.17)$$

(Barrasso and Ramachandran, 2015; Iveson et al., 2001) provides a thorough methodology for comprehending how liquid binder distribution affects agglomeration formation and stability through the methodological focus on determining external liquid volume. Liquid layer height is determined by the external liquid film volume as shown in equation 2.18.

$$h = \frac{V_{liq,ext}}{\alpha_{vol} d_{granule}^2} \quad (2.18)$$

The external surface layer liquid volume is determined by a simple mass balance as shown in equation 2.19.

$$V_{liq,ext} = V_{liq} - \epsilon_{granule} V_{granule} \frac{s^*}{1 - s^*} \quad (2.19)$$

The agglomerate envelope porosity is determined using a model derived from experiments as explained in 2.2.5.1.

2.2.4 CFD-DEM

CFD-DEM is a sophisticated numerical method used to simulate systems that involve interaction between fluid and discrete solid particles. This method merges the capabilities of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), which resolves the fluid dynamics equations, with the Discrete Element Method (DEM), which models the behavior of individual particles.

Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) is a numerical approach to solve and evaluate fluid flow problems. CFD focuses on solving the Navier-Stokes equations, which govern the movement of fluids. The equations are a system of nonlinear partial differential equations that maintain the conservation of mass, momentum and energy in a fluid.

Discrete Element Method (DEM) is a numerical approach used to model the interactions and behavior of individual particles within a system. DEM uses Newton's second law of motion to compute the path of each particle by taking into account the forces and moments that affect it.

Combining CFD and DEM requires solving fluid dynamics equations (CFD) and tracking the movement of individual particles (DEM) at the same time. The main difficulty in integrating CFD-DEM is in accurately representing the interactions between the fluid and particles, such as drag force, buoyancy and virtual mass forces.

According to Kloss et al., 2012, two modeling methodologies for coupled systems are used: (i) unresolved and (ii) resolved CFD-DEM. The unresolved technique is used when the particle size is less than the computational grid, therefore the particles are not entirely occupying a cell. In

cases where the particle size exceeds the CFD grid, the resolved approach is used, given that particles cover multiple cells. In this study the unresolved approach is used.

Equations 2.20 and 2.21 describe the continuity and motion of an incompressible fluid phase with a particulate phase modeled using the volume-averaged Navier-Stokes equations.

$$\frac{\partial \alpha_f}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_f \mathbf{u}_f) = 0 \quad (2.20)$$

$$\frac{\partial (\alpha_f \mathbf{u}_f)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_f \mathbf{u}_f \mathbf{u}_f) = -\alpha_f \nabla \frac{p}{\rho_f} - \mathbf{R}_{pf} + \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau} \quad (2.21)$$

Here, α_f represents the volume fraction of the fluid, ρ_f is the fluid's density, \mathbf{u}_f is the fluid's velocity and $\boldsymbol{\tau} = \nu_f \nabla \mathbf{u}_f$ represents the stress tensor of the fluid phase. \mathbf{R}_{pf} denotes the momentum transfer with the particulate phase, determined in each cell by accumulating for example the drag forces acting on the particles.

A more comprehensive description of CFD-DEM can be found in Zhou et al., 2010 and Kieckhefen et al., 2020.

2.2.4.1 Setup

All CFD-DEM simulations are executed with the software CFDEMcoupling (Goniva et al., 2012) which couples LIGGGHTS (Kloss et al., 2012) with OpenFOAM (Weller et al., 1998).

The meshing was carried out utilizing snappyHexMesh, a hexahedral cut-cell mesher, within OpenFOAM. The lengths of the sides of the cells are provided in table 2.6 and the final mesh is displayed in figure 2.3.

The time step for DEM is selected as a fraction (15%) of the Rayleigh and Hertzian time. The CFD time step, adheres to the Courant-Friedrich-Lewy criterion. The time step is adjusted to keep the Courant number below 1. The particle and wall material and contact properties together with the numerical specifications are given in table 2.6. The Young's modulus of particles is lowered to allow larger time steps and a reduction in computation time. The density is set to a similar value as the envelope density of the material. Contact forces are calculated according to the Hertz-Mindlin-Tsuji law Tsuji et al., 1992. The rolling friction is modelled using the elastic plastic spring dashpot torque model epsd2 Ai et al., 2011. The drag forces are calculated using the model of Beetstra et al., 2007.

FIGURE 2.3: Mesh of GF3.

TABLE 2.6: Numerical settings and particle and wall properties of CFD-DEM setup.

Parameter	Units	Value
Numerics		
Time step CFD	s	5E-04
Time step DEM	s	1E-05
Coupling interval	-	50
Particle scaling factor	-	8
Particle & wall		
Diameter	μm	PSD 1-6
Density	kg/m^3	900
Young's modulus p	Pa	1E+06
Young's modulus w	Pa	5E+08
Poisson ratio	-	0.25
Restitution coefficient p-p	-	0.8

TABLE 2.6: Numerical settings and particle and wall properties of CFD-DEM setup.

Parameter	Units	Value
Restitution coefficient p-w	-	0.8
Friction coefficient p-p	-	0.3
Friction coefficient p-w	-	0.3
Rolling friction coefficient p-p	-	0.05
Rolling friction coefficient p-w	-	0.05
Mesh		
Cellsize	m	0.01

The number of particles with the PSD displayed in table 2.7 yields too many particles to simulate therefore a particle scaling factor of 8 is applied.

TABLE 2.7: Particle size distributions for CFD-DEM.

Diameter	Unit	PSD 1	PSD 2	PSD 3	PSD 4	PSD 5	PSD 6
d1	μm	97	119	140	162	184	205
d2	μm	137	171	204	237	271	304
d3	μm	173	217	261	306	350	395
d4	μm	220	279	337	395	453	511
d5	μm	326	412	499	585	671	757

18 simulations are executed as listed in table 2.8. The simulations vary the PSD from table 2.7 and the inlet velocity matching the experiments upper and lower limit and a center point.

TABLE 2.8: CFD-DEM simulations with respective parameters.

Case	PSD	Inlet velocity [m/s]
1	1	0.65

TABLE 2.8: CFD-DEM simulations with respective parameters.

Case	PSD	Inlet velocity [m/s]
2	2	0.65
3	3	0.65
4	4	0.65
5	5	0.65
6	6	0.65
7	1	0.87
8	2	0.87
9	3	0.87
10	4	0.87
11	5	0.87
12	6	0.87
13	1	1.09
14	2	1.09
15	3	1.09
16	4	1.09
17	5	1.09
18	6	1.09

2.2.5 Development of surrogate models

The procedure to develop surrogate models from CFD-DEM simulations is described in this subsection. It describes the statistical methods that are applied to the analysis of the simulation data in order to derive significant correlations between the simulation parameters and the desired outputs (particle wetness, velocity). The accuracy of the surrogate models is assessed using performance indicators mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) and coefficient of determination (R^2). Furthermore, sensitivity analysis was performed to determine how altering input parameters

affected the model's predictions. The predictive power of the models was confirmed by this investigation, which also provided insight into the relative significance of various parameters influencing particle movements in fluidized beds. This work provides a useful and effective substitute for direct CFD-DEM simulations through the development of these surrogate models, which will allow for more accurate prediction and management of particle agglomeration processes in fluidized beds.

2.2.5.1 Porosity model

This chapter presents a novel surrogate model that uses the maximum moisture content and agglomeration size as its main input variables for predicting the porosity of agglomerated particles in fluidized beds. The model delivers a novel way to understand and regulate the physical properties of agglomerated solids. It is generated from simple experimental measurements of tap and bulk density.

The application of the model in predicting and improving particle porosity in fluidized bed agglomeration processes is investigated and illustrated in chapter 2.3.3. Sensitivity analysis demonstrates how the model can provide direction for operational decisions, such as altering moisture levels and processing conditions, in order to attain the desired porosity characteristics in the final product.

Measurement of the tap and bulk density is described in the following paragraphs. It allows to determine the agglomerate envelope density.

$$\rho_{env} = \frac{m_s}{V_s + V_p} \quad (2.22)$$

The envelope density of the agglomerate includes inter particle pores inside the agglomerate, open and closed intra particle pores of the primary particles.

$$V_p = V_{p,open} + V_{p,closed} \quad (2.23)$$

The bulk and tap density of a material are primarily determined by the particle packing fraction, which is influenced by the PSD (Hoffmann and Finkers, 1995). The presence of a wide range of particle sizes in a polydisperse PSD has a significant impact on the bulk and tap density. In case of a monodisperse PSD the density of the material is mostly influenced by the shape of the particles. The tap density of a sample with a narrow size range serves as a measure of envelope density, as it can be assumed that a consistent packing fraction applies to each measurement. To ensure a narrow distribution, the material in this study was sieved using a sieve tower before

measuring the tap density. The four utilized sieve size classes are: 300, 560, 710 and 1000 μm . The bed porosity of a settled bed typically lies between the range of 0.36 to 0.38 (Dullien, 1979; Hoffmann and Finkers, 1995). For the purposes of this investigation, a value of 0.38 is considered. The bed porosity is calculated as follows:

$$1 - \epsilon_{bed} = \frac{V_s + V_p}{V_{tap}} \quad (2.24)$$

The envelope density is then determined by combining equations 2.22, 2.4 and 2.24 to equation 2.25.

$$\rho_{env} = \frac{m_s}{V_s + V_p} = \frac{m_s}{V_{tap}(1 - \epsilon_{bed})} = \frac{\rho_{tap}}{1 - \epsilon_{bed}} \quad (2.25)$$

The envelope porosity can then be derived as follows in equation 2.26.

$$\epsilon_{env} = \frac{V_p}{V_s + V_p} = \frac{(V_p + V_s) - V_s}{V_p + V_s} = 1 - \frac{V_s}{V_s + V_p} = 1 - \frac{m_s \rho_{env}}{\rho_s m_s} = 1 - \frac{\rho_{env}}{\rho_s} \quad (2.26)$$

With the derived agglomerate porosity from simple weighing and volume measurements it is possible to build a simple model shown in equation 2.27. The agglomerates are produced during fluidized bed agglomeration. Due to the creation of inter particle void upon agglomeration the agglomerate porosity increases with agglomerate size. Utilizing the maximum moisture content and the sieving classes allows to develop a simple porosity model. The model is limited to values between 0 and 1 to maintain correct physical values.

$$\epsilon_{env,agglo} = C_1 MC_{max} + C_2 d + C_3 \quad (2.27)$$

2.2.5.2 Particle wetting model

In fluidized bed agglomeration, it is essential to achieve appropriate wetting of particles in order to maintain the same quality of agglomerates. This chapter presents a basic surrogate model intended for predicting the wetting distribution of particles. This distribution plays an essential part in determining the agglomeration probability since liquid is used as a binding mechanism. The basis of this model is the thorough studies conducted by CFD-DEM simulations, specifically designed to investigate the dynamics within a predetermined cylindrical spray zone. These simulations are an essential tool for comprehending the complex relationship between fluid dynamics and particle interactions that are fundamental to the wetting process.

Precisely forecasting and attaining the most favourable wetting distribution poses significant difficulties, considering the intricate dynamics involved. The issues include the difference in particle sizes, the diversity of spray mechanisms and the impact of operational parameters such as fluidization velocity and spray flowrate of liquid and gas. Although all of these mechanisms can be addressed using comprehensive physics-based CFD-DEM simulations, setting up such simulations can be exceedingly complicated. The emphasis is on employing more straightforward methods that may be less precise but require fewer resources.

The simulations are pre run to establish a steady state of the fluidization behavior. The residence time is then tracked over 3 seconds and the arithmetic mean average over all particles of the same size is determined as shown in equation 2.28.

$$t_{res,d} = \frac{\sum_i t_{i,d}}{n_{p,d}} \quad (2.28)$$

The mean residence time is then normalized with the simulation time to gain the dimensionless residence time τ as shown in equation 2.29.

$$\tau = \frac{t_{res}}{t_{sim}} \quad (2.29)$$

A simple model for the dimensionless residence time as a function of inlet velocity and particle size is derived as shown in equation 2.30.

$$\tau = C_1 u + C_2 d + C_3 \quad (2.30)$$

The predicted dimensionless residence time is normalized to 2.31.

$$\tau_{norm,i} = \frac{\tau_i}{\sum_i \tau_i} \quad (2.31)$$

The liquid injection flow rate is multiplied with the liquid distribution to gain the wetting rate of each size class as shown in equation 2.32.

$$\dot{m}_{wet,i} = \frac{\tau_i d_i^2}{\sum_i \tau_i d_i^2} \dot{m}_{spray} \quad (2.32)$$

2.3 Results

2.3.1 Porosity analysis

The initial material has an envelope porosity of 980 kg/m^3 . This value is similar to the envelope density of similar materials found in literature Pashminehazar et al., 2016. After agglomeration in the fluidized bed the envelope porosity decreases in some cases to 250 kg/m^3 . Similarly the bulk density also decreases from 564 kg/m^3 of the initial material to 180 kg/m^3 after agglomeration in some cases. The model developed in chapter 2.2.5.1 fits with an accuracy of 97% (MAPE).

FIGURE 2.4: Parity plot showing the predicted porosity compared to the measured porosity.

The porosity of the final product is very high. The model covers a wide porosity range from 0.57 up to 0.82. The model needs to be extended with porosity measurements between the final product and the initial material to confirm the model also holds for porosities between 0.35 and 0.57. It is assumed that the envelope porosity of the primary particles does not change. Due to the creation of inter particle void the envelope porosity of the agglomerates increases.

2.3.2 Mean residence time analysis

The residence time determines the time a particle spends in the spray zone. This is an indication of the exposure of a particle to the spray and the liquid droplets. The residence time is influenced by many factors as the bed mass, particles size and inlet air velocity. The model developed in chapter 2.2.5.2 fits with an accuracy of 91% (MAPE).

FIGURE 2.5: Parity plot showing the predicted dimensionless residence time compared to the dimensionless residence time from CFD-DEM simulations.

2.3.3 Fluidized bed agglomeration

The agglomeration of maltodextrin in a fluidized bed is influenced by many factors like the moisture content, temperature and size of the particles. This chapter analyses the agglomeration of maltodextrin using different models and displays the influence of model parameters and process parameters. The following results are created with the calibrated model of Rajniak et al., 2009. The particles grow in size as displayed in figure 2.6 and reach an equilibrium after about 15 minutes. The equilibrium size d_{50} is accurately predicted while the d_{90} is underestimated and the d_{10} overestimated. This shows that the model gives a good indication of the equilibrium size but has difficulties of capturing the change of the width of the distribution. In all three

instances d_{10} , d_{50} and d_{90} the particle size increases faster than the experiment and then growth slows down drastically.

FIGURE 2.6: Particle size d_{10} , d_{50} and d_{90} over time at an inlet air temperature of 100°C , inlet air flow rate of $100\text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ and a spray water mass flow rate of $18\text{ g}/\text{min}$.

The moisture content increases over time as the spray is turned on and reaches an equilibrium. As shown in figure 2.7 the heat and mass transfer resulting in the particle moisture content is well captured by the models. The moisture content equilibrium is reached after about 5 minutes.

FIGURE 2.7: Moisture content over time at an inlet air temperature of 100°C , inlet air flow rate of $100\text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ and a spray water mass flow rate of $18\text{ g}/\text{min}$.

The design space exploration of the spray water mass flow rate and the inlet air temperature is shown exemplary. The design space exploration allows to predict the conditions in the process

chamber at different times and process parameters using a calibrated PBM model. The results shown in the following paragraphs are created by calibrating the Rajniak et al., 2009 model. The particle size increases with spray mass flow rate and decreases with inlet air temperature. The equilibrium agglomerate size can be estimated from figure 2.8.

FIGURE 2.8: Equilibrium average particle size as a function of inlet air temperature and spray mass flow rate at an inlet air flow rate of $100 \text{ m}^3/h$.

The resulting particle moisture content in equilibrium at different spray water mass flow rate and the inlet air temperature is displayed in figure 2.9.

FIGURE 2.9: Equilibrium moisture content as a function of inlet air temperature and spray mass flow rate at an inlet air flow rate of $100 \text{ m}^3/h$.

The resulting particle temperature in equilibrium at different spray water mass flow rate and the inlet air temperature is displayed in figure 2.10.

FIGURE 2.10: Equilibrium temperature as a function of inlet air temperature and spray mass flow rate at an inlet air flow rate of $100 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$.

2.4 Challenges and outlook

The use of surrogate modeling for PBM with DEM is a complex and demanding task that aims to combine detailed simulations with computing efficiency. The objective of this integration is to imitate the complex behaviour of particulate systems while minimizing computational expenses. Nevertheless, there are certain obstacles that limit the integration, use and development of surrogate models.

The primary difficulty derives from the inherent complex and random behaviour of particle systems that are represented by DEM models. To effectively represent the complex interactions between particles and the resulting characteristics on a larger scale using a surrogate model, a solid understanding of the fundamental physics and sophisticated data-driven approaches is necessary. The accuracy of these surrogate models is essential, as errors might result in substantial deviations when predicting system responses. One constraint is the ability of surrogate models to make generalizations. These models are usually trained or calibrated using specific system

configurations and operating settings and their capability to forecast behaviour under new conditions may be limited. This limitation decreases their usefulness to only a few specific situations, which reduces their effectiveness in predicting outcomes for new systems or in different operational conditions.

An additional significant obstacle is the range and variety of the input parameter space. DEM simulations of particulate systems involve numerous input parameters, such as particle size distribution, shape and material properties among other factors. To effectively explore this high-dimensional space and provide accurate predictions under different conditions, the development of a surrogate model requires the proper capturing of underlying physics. Surrogate models, due to their simplified representation of a system may not completely capture the complex physics resolved by DEM simulations, resulting in possible differences between predicted and observed system behaviours.

Furthermore, the incorporation of surrogate models into PBM involves converting interactions between single particles on totally different time scale into a continuous representation that appropriately represents the overall population's behaviour. This translation adds additional complexity and error, necessitating innovative methodologies to guarantee that essential information is not compromised or lost during the process of simplification.

Additionally, the development of surrogate models is limited by the accessibility and accuracy of the training data. Acquiring a sufficiently large dataset from DEM simulations requires a significant amount of computer resources and effort. Due to this constraint, it is necessary to generate data in order to create a thorough training dataset that accurately captures the behaviour of the system.

Thorough validation and measurement of uncertainty are necessary when integrating surrogate models with DEM for PBM in order to establish confidence in the model's predictions. The resource requirements and complexity of this approach can undermine the computational efficiency advantages of surrogate models.

2.5 Conclusion

The development of surrogate models based on CFD-DEM simulations and the introduction of a novel agglomeration kernel that combines the features existing kernels in a more mechanistic approach constitute a major advancement in the modeling and optimization of particle agglomeration processes in fluidized beds. The study's conclusions highlight how these developments could improve the effectiveness, control and understanding of agglomeration processes in industrial settings. High accuracy and efficiency have been established by the surrogate models that have been developed to predict particle wetting and porosity. These models, which greatly minimize

the computational resources needed in comparison to direct CFD-DEM simulations, are a useful tools for rapid process assessment and optimization by accurately capturing the complex behavior of particle interactions in fluidized beds.

More mechanistic approaches combining simulations and experiments will be required to speed up and improve the accuracy of simulations. The availability of increasing computing power will make it simpler to retrieve more data from calibrated frameworks like CFD-DEM. By incorporating essential elements of particle coalescence, the novel agglomeration kernel created in this work provides a more precise and thorough depiction of agglomeration processes. This kernel expands the application of population balance models to a larger range of fluidized bed operations while also enhancing their predictive power through its mechanistic nature.

Applying surrogate models and a novel agglomeration kernel to fluidized bed agglomerators has yielded useful insights for optimizing agglomeration processes. The design space exploration demonstrates the capacity of these tools to provide insight into the design and process parameter settings of fluidized beds, resulting in improved product quality and process efficiency. The results of this work provide opportunities for further investigation, in improving and expanding the surrogate models and agglomeration kernel to include more physical phenomena and operational variables. Examining the incorporation of these models with real-time monitoring and control systems could facilitate their use in adaptive process optimization.

The implementation of these models can have a substantial influence on the design, optimization and scaling of fluidized bed agglomerators from an industrial standpoint. Predicting and controlling particle behavior during agglomeration processes has the potential to greatly enhance efficiency, cost-effectiveness and product uniformity.

This study highlights the significance of employing creative modeling methods to enhance the understanding and control of complex industrial processes. The findings reported here reflect a significant step forward in the search of more efficient, effective and mechanistic particle agglomeration methods.

2.6 Best practice guidelines

The combination of surrogate modeling in PBM utilizing DEM or CFD-DEM frameworks offers a promising approach for enhancing the efficiency of industrial operations in the field of fluidized bed agglomeration. However, in order to effectively navigate the complex nature of these simulations and fully utilize the capabilities of these models and methods, it is essential to have a thorough set of guidelines. The purpose of these guidelines is to achieve an appropriate balance between computing efficiency and the precision and relevance of the models in various industrial contexts. The initial guideline emphasizes the complex nature and computation

demands involved in conducting comprehensive full physics simulations in CFD-DEM. Although these simulations provide in-depth understanding of fluidized bed agglomeration processes, their substantial computing expense restricts their feasibility for real-time or large-scale industrial implementations. It is essential to acknowledge these compromises in order to decide when to use complete simulations as opposed to surrogate models or PBM stand alone or alternative methods.

By adding detailed particle-level interactions, the integration of DEM or CFD-DEM with PBM strengthens the prediction capabilities of PBM. Nevertheless, this coupling can considerably slow down simulations, hence compromising the efficiency of PBM. Industries should thoroughly assess the need and scope of online coupling, prioritizing efficient techniques that strike a compromise between accurate physical representation and computing efficiency. This might involve employing selective coupling or utilizing hybrid models that exclusively couple the methods for essential evaluations.

Empirical surrogate models, especially those utilizing machine learning, provide a convenient method to forecast the results of fluidized bed agglomeration processes. Nevertheless, the dependence on calibration and the restricted validity to particular geometries, materials and process parameters combinations restrict their direct use. Industries ought to allocate resources towards acquiring extensive datasets that encompass a wide array of operational situations and material attributes. These datasets will be used to train the models effectively. Periodic updates and recalibrations are essential when new data is obtained or when process conditions change. Mechanistic models provide a cost-effective alternative to complex simulations, making them suitable for rapid predictions or first evaluations. Nevertheless, their inability to capture the entirety of complex physics or to apply generally across many scenarios is a common phenomenon. Mechanistic models remain more general than empirical correlations but should always be applied within their range of validity. An essential aspect of using surrogate models in industrial applications is the thorough validation of these models using experimental or simulation data.

In case of stand alone PBM the use of multi-dimensional PBM for fluidized bed agglomeration is possible to achieve a detailed understanding of particulate processes. This is accomplished by simultaneously taking into account several particle properties including size, shape and composition. This methodology improves the precision of process forecasts by considering various features of particles that impact the dynamics of fluidized beds. Nevertheless, the complex nature of multi-dimensional PBM equations escalates the computational requirements, underscoring the necessity for sophisticated numerical techniques and high-performance computing to successfully address these issues.

Similarly, the use of multi-compartment PBM brings a spatial dimension to modeling, by separating the fluidized bed into many compartments to represent the variation in particle

behavior across different sections of the bed. This approach enhances the model's capacity to accurately represent the fluctuations in process conditions and particle interactions, hence providing a more detailed prediction of agglomeration results. Calibrating and validating multi-compartment models necessitate extensive spatial information, which presents a substantial problem due to the complexity of obtaining such measurements in experiments. This is where complex simulation methods like CFD-DEM are necessary to fill the missing information.

Ultimately, utilizing surrogate modeling for PBM in fluidized bed agglomeration processes presents an opportunity to improve comprehension and optimization of the process, while also reducing the processing demands of conventional CFD-DEM simulations. Industries can effectively and efficiently apply these principles to manage the difficulties involved with these models, hence boosting process performance and decision-making. At this point the use of generative artificial intelligence technology is expected to bring a considerable evolution in surrogate modelling. An especially encouraging option is the advancement of mechanistic digital twins that are based on physical equations rather than solely relying on empirical methods. This groundbreaking advancement involves using generative AI to autonomously derive and enhance mechanistic models by incorporating fundamental physical concepts, such as conservation laws and kinematic correlations. Contrary to conventional empirical surrogate models, which are confined to the circumstances in which they were trained, these AI-generated mechanistic models possess the ability to flexibly adjust to new data and offer insights into the underlying physics of the process. Currently, the utilization of AI for mechanistic surrogate modeling is still a concept that is yet to be realized.

Chapter 3

CFD-DEM-PBM Upscaling for Jet Mills

3.1 Introduction

Milling and grinding processes underwent many evolutionary changes in the last few decades. High-speed computing capabilities played a major role in making better machines and helped to identify optimum operating conditions. Numerical methods such as CFD and DEM helped to understand the black-box milling and grinding systems better. In other words, modeling black-box systems with the help of simulation methods. Modeling a process or machine in the earlier days involved analyzing the effect of parameters and describing it via empirical equations [Morrell and Man, 1997]. Though the method works to some extent with linear scaling, it could not accurately account for the effect of the geometrical features of the equipment. The process also involves a lot of scaled prototyping and experiments. In the context of milling and grinding, predicting the outcome of a machine was mainly done with the help of empirical equations and population balance methods [Berthiaux and Dodds, 1999; Gupta, 2022].

In the current document, the industrial applicability of a new method is investigated for a fluidized-bed opposed jet mill. This type of jet mill is used for applications involving the processing of high-value powders with high purity requirements. The fluidized-bed opposed jet mill invented by Luckenbach and Wolfenden (1881), can achieve particle sizes in the micron scale. The breakage mechanism of the mill naturally supports very low contamination. The jet mill is also preferred for those materials which react to temperature changes. These properties make the mill suitable for the food, cosmetics, and pharmaceutical industries. The breakage mechanism of this type of mill is still a subject of active research.

FIGURE 3.1: Fluidized-bed opposed jet mill

3.2 Methodology

Modeling the jet milling process using CFD-DEM-PBM involves certain steps. The details of those steps will be presented in this section. Modeling granular processes such as agglomeration, breakage etc. involves steps that ask for creative solutions. In most cases, there is no standardized procedure to be followed to get a certain result. Very often it depends on the number of available resources, such as a high-speed camera, mechanical workshop, people around with technical skills, special laboratories, computational-skills [Bruchmüller et al., 2011] etc. It is up to the researcher to make the optimum use of resources to come up with a solution.

3.2.1 Impact breakage characterization

The first step in modeling the jet mill is to understand how breakage occurs inside the mill. In a jet mill, particle breakage mainly happens by particle-particle collisions. The particles are accelerated with the help of high pressure air jets causing the particles to collide with each other at the centre.

Each collision leads to either damage accumulation or direct breakage of the particle. Due to the system's complexity and highly turbulent nature of flow, it is not easy to collect data from inside the mill to see how the particle breaks. When the particle sizes are in the micron range, characterizing the breakage properties of particles becomes challenging. There are a lot of creative ways to set up an impact breakage characterization device. It can take any form depending on the material availability and resources. The expected output from the device is a relationship between impact energy, breakage energy, damage accumulation and progeny size distribution (breakage function) for the particles under investigation. This subsection describes the breakage characterization methods found in the literature along with the setup used by the author to characterize particle breakage via impact.

FIGURE 3.2: Different sections of an opposed jet mill

FIGURE 3.3: Impact breakage calibration devices found in literature

Scirocco tube

Originally developed by the Ghadiri group [Ali et al., 2015; Bonakdar et al., 2016] at Leeds to characterize the grinding properties of particles. Particles are forced through an angled tube to a particle size measurement device. The particles break at the L- joint when the flow takes a 90-degree turn whereas the particles end up hitting the tube wall.

Rotary devices

The JKBRT [Shi et al., 2009] inspired from Schonert [Marktscheffel and Schönert, 1986] uses a roto-stator mechanism. The particles are impacted against the stator leading to particle breakage.

Horizontal impactors

The horizontal impactor [Petukhov and Kalman, 2003; Rozenblat et al., 2012] is one of the easiest impact testers to build for characterizing particle breakage. The device shoots particles at high velocity against a wall, and the broken particles are collected from the base and analyzed.

BASF pin mill

The device is a modified target mill from BASF. The feed material is accelerated along a shaft and dispersed into a channel with metal pins acting as obstacles for the flow. The dispersed particles hit the pin (repeatedly) and break on their way to the cyclone.

FIGURE 3.4: BASF pin mill schematic

By adjusting the number of pins and varying the inlet pressures, different breakage scenarios during the operation of an actual jet mill can be emulated with the machine setup. The broken particles are analyzed to calculate the breakage function, breakage propensity and energy threshold. The BASF pin mill was chosen primarily because the same simulation settings could be used on the actual jet mill. The BASF mill uses an air jet pistol with a 2 mm nozzle diameter which is the same as the opposed jet mill the iPAT, TU Braunschweig.

3.2.2 CFD-DEM calibration

Simulations aid in unraveling the intricacies of black-box systems like a jet mill, offering insights into their underlying phenomena. However, the validity of this understanding is contingent upon the accuracy with which simulation parameters are calibrated. In the current project, open-source packages - liggghts, cfdemCoupling and OpenFOAM are used for simulations. An explanation of the working principle and underlying mathematical aspects in each of the above numerical solvers can be found elsewhere [Ferziger and Perić, 2002; Goniva et al., 2012; Kloss et al., 2012].

FIGURE 3.5: BASF pin mill simulation

The approach followed in the current project involves using the simulation settings of a validated test case in the simulation setup of the jet mill. The BASF pin mill is used as the validation case. The experimental setup (ref Figure 3.4) has the following elements - connection to a high-pressure line, pressure gauges, a feed with a narrow size distribution, plexiglass model of the mill, high-speed camera and lighting arrangement, cyclone and particle measurement devices. Using the high-speed camera, particle velocities were measured for various inlet pressures and feed sizes. The values are compared against CFD-DEM simulations for selection and fine-tuning of the coupling parameters for drag models in the cfdemCoupling package. Experiment specifications are given below:

Jet pressure (bar) - 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7

Feed - battery slag - 164, 260, 355 μm

High speed camera - 20000 Hz frame rate

Particle size measurements - Mastersizer, Hand-sieves

The same experimental setup is used for finding the breakage properties of particles, especially the breakage propensity parameter, f_{mat} and $W_{m,min}$ in equation 3.1.

FIGURE 3.6: High-speed camera experiments

3.2.3 Breakage model

A breakage model [Beke, 1964] describes how a particle responds to impacts endured in the simulation system. There are several breakage models available in literature such as the Vogel and Peukert model [Vogel and Peukert, 2005], Tavares model [Tavares, 2017], UCM model [Powell et al., 2008] to name a few. The choice of breakage model influences how a breakage event is accounted in a system. A breakage model together with a breakage function completes the implementation of a particle breakage simulation. This explains 'when' and 'how' particles are broken down into progeny particles. These are two essential components to build a population balance model (PBM) based on experiments.

In the current project, the Vogel and Peukert model (3.1) is adopted as the breakage model. The model incorporates the effect of multiple collisions and thereby damage accumulation. There are 2 unknown parameters in the model equation whose values can be found using the BASF pin mill and the calibration procedure mentioned in the previous section.

$$S = 1 - \exp\{-f_{mat} \cdot x \cdot k \cdot (W_m - W_{m,min})\} \quad (3.1)$$

where, S is the probability of breakage in a single breakage event, f_{mat} is a material breakage propensity parameter, x is the particle size, $W_{m,min}$ is the minimum specific energy to initiate breakage in a material. k refers to the number of collisions taken by the particle with a specific energy W_m .

The breakage function [Kelly and Spottiswood, 1990], B_{ij} characterizes both the distribution of fragment sizes and the number of fragments resulting from the breakage of a particle. It can be obtained from any of the experiments mentioned in the previous section. We can find a lot of named breakage functions, which can be used to fit the data from experiments. Tavares, Vogel and Peukert, and Austin to name a few. These fitting functions are useful in solving the PBM numerically.

$$B_{ij} = 1 - (1 - t_{10})^{(9/(d_0/D_1)-1)^\alpha} \quad (3.2)$$

Above shown is the Tavares and King [King and Cross, 2003] breakage function which is used in the current implementation.

3.2.4 PBM implementation

A population balance model describes the spatial and temporal evolution of the particle size distribution [Capece et al., 2014]. The population balance equation of a grinding process takes the below form:

$$\frac{dm_i(t)}{dt} = \underbrace{-k_i(t)m_i(t)}_{\text{I}} + \underbrace{\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} b_{ij}k_j(t)m_j(t)}_{\text{II}} \quad (3.3)$$

The term on the LHS denotes the time rate of change of species mass fraction in size classes i . In the RHS, term I refers to the rate at which mass fraction from size class i disappears and term II denotes the accumulation of mass fraction from bigger size classes j into size class i . $k_i(t)$ is the specific breakage rate (selection) parameter. In reality, it is a function of t but one often assumes a constant value in grinding applications. b_{ij} is the breakage function.

In the current CFD-DEM-PBM framework, we calculate $k_i(t)$ as a function of particle collision frequency from the CFD-DEM simulation [Capece et al., 2014]. At steady state operating condition of the mill, the value of $k_i(t)$ stabilizes and one can assume it as a constant. To find the value of k_i at steady state, we need to run the CFD-DEM simulation and wait till the calculated $k_i(t)$ reaches a steady value. In an opposed jet mill, the system reaches a pseudo-steady state in less than 0.01 s. k_i is calculated as follows:

$$k_i = f_{mat}x_i \sum_{l=1}^L f_{coll,l}(E_{m,l} - E_{m,min}) \quad (3.4)$$

where $f_{coll,l}$ is the collision frequency in energy class l .

k_i in the above equation can be interpreted as a weighted function of $f_{coll,l}$ where each energy class, $E_{m,l} - E_{m,min}$ are the corresponding weights. Here each energy class is an "effective" specific breakage energy rather than an absolute specific energy of collision.

FIGURE 3.7: Communication between OpenFOAM, liggghts and PBM module

The PBM module does not communicate directly with the CFD part. The model receives its input from the DEM solver. Hence the model is built entirely on top of the open-source DEM solver - liggghts. The user has to input all the material breakage-related properties into the DEM script which is read by the PBM module. The model proceeds to work alongside the CFD-DEM coupled solver and prints out necessary data for visualization in real time.

FIGURE 3.8: Data pipeline for the PBM module

For an accurate description of the PBM, the calculation of k should encompass the system dynamics in its entirety. This means that the calculated k from the simulation must be derived from an identical condition in a real mill. Assuming batch operating conditions in both simulation and real mill system, after a certain time $t = t_1$, we make the following observations:

- Part of the feed in the actual mill is pulverized and a fraction of it is transported to the classifier and collected as a 'fine' product
- In the simulation system, we have the same number of particles being subjected to repeated collisions despite exceeding the energy threshold for breakage. This causes an error in the calculation of k_i

The above situation calls for alternative ways to account for particle breakage in a simulation system. The upcoming sections discuss the various numerical possibilities to mimic the events in an actual jet mill.

3.2.5 Simulation strategies for particle breakage

In jet mills, the broken-down particles are continuously carried away through the transport zone. This is due to the pressure difference between the grinding region and the classifier region. This calls for the need to design and implement alternative approaches to account for breakage in a simulation system.

Vanishing particle method: In this method, whenever a particle surpasses the set threshold for breakage condition, it is removed from the system thereby giving the rest of the particles a higher chance for breakage. On the contrary, the method fails to account for the presence of fine progeny particles as a result of breakage. This method is implemented in the current DEM code. But its practicality as a breakage representation method requires rigorous validation dataset.

Particle replacement method [Bruchmüller et al., 2011]: The particle to be broken is replaced by smaller progeny particles. Though this gives the most accurate description of particle breakage in a milling system, it is impractical due to the exponential increase in the number of particles in the system giving rise to high computational costs and poor scalability.

Ghost particle method: The marked particle to be broken is replaced with another smaller particle with modified properties to mitigate the drawbacks of the vanishing particle method. The new particle does not break further and is supposed to act as a friction force between particles similar to how fine particles behave in a grinding system. This approach is a concept and needs further investigation and validation.

Lubrication method [Chèvremont et al., 2020]: The presence of fine or semi-fine particles in the simulation system can be accounted for with a lubrication force between the particles. However, the extent of this force needs to be calculated based on specially designed experiments. In Chapter 4, we delve into the implementation of the lubrication model. There, we discuss a scenario where the material intended for milling exists virtually, without a physical presence in the simulated mill. However, its impact is considered within the system with the help of lubrication forces.

3.2.6 Methodology summary

The current implementation, which is a work in progress, aims to solve the population balance equation for milling applications during simulation run-time. Many grinding and milling systems reach a pseudo steady-state soon after the process starts. However, for practical reasons, it is difficult to identify when the system reaches a steady regime. Using the implemented DEM-PBM approach, one can calculate the time at which the system reaches a steady state so that the specific grinding rate at that point can be used to predict the product evolution for the entire system.

3.3 Results

The end goal of the project is to develop and implement a CFD-DEM-PBM framework to make predictions about product output in jet milling processes. The framework should also help to

make informed decisions on the operating conditions of the mill. Finally, the model should help create geometrically optimized machines in the domain of milling and grinding. On the onset of completion of the implementation, the same will be used to predict the PSD from an opposed jet mill.

3.3.1 Which mill design is better!?

To demonstrate the capability of the current model under development, below arbitrary cases are used. Three mill designs are presented and the task is to pick the best-performing one based on the implementation of the specific grinding rate function implemented in the code.

FIGURE 3.9: 3 corrugated mill designs

The above three designs vary only in the design of the corrugation. Each has a cube, conical, and finally, a monkey head-shaped corrugation cross-section respectively. Each is filled with the same amount of feed material and rotated at the same rpm. The simulation is run with identical settings. The material and breakage properties are arbitrary. The simulation also assumes that the minimum threshold energy of the material is 0 and is run for 2 seconds and the drums rotate at 0.5 rad/s. The result of the analysis is shown below. The particles remain in the simulation throughout the run-time.

The cone corrugated mill shows better performance compared to the other mills. If we run the simulation long enough, we see that k almost reaches a constant value. The value of k also depends on the averaging method used in the implementation.

3.3.2 Opposed jet mill simulations

The fluidized bed opposed jet mill is a complex system to model and simulate. Extreme pressure and velocity gradients at the nozzle and a rotating classifier make simulation a challenging endeavor. Combining the above with a discrete particle system adds further complications. This calls for a lot of compromises in the modeling methodology. Below given picture gives an idea of how the simulation domain is simplified to make a feasible simulation.

FIGURE 3.10: Data obtained during the simulation

FIGURE 3.11: Simulation domain simplification steps

The coupled CFD-DEM simulation of the opposed jet mill is currently not available since the simulation is computationally expensive and takes weeks to generate a transient case. A detailed analysis of the full jet mill will be available in the coming months.

3.4 Challenges and outlook

Emulating the behavior of physical systems using nonphysical numerical techniques is inherently complex. This complexity is compounded by the obvious challenge of accessing various jet mills for experimental verification, further hindered by the scarcity of validation cases in the existing literature.

Setting up the CFD-DEM case for the jet mill is a challenge. The accuracy of coupled simulations depend on a lot of factors including CFD cell size, coupling interval, choice of drag force, boundary conditions etc. Arriving at the most accurate setup is a result of countless trial and error tries especially when working with open-source packages such as liggghts or OpenFOAM. There are numerous occasions where the solver does not have the right utility, one has to add it themselves just so that they can reach the point that matters. These intermediate pitstops has costed a lot of time and effort.

Given that the primary focus of the project revolves around PBM upscaling, it is essential to thoroughly grasp the underlying solver upon which we construct the PBM module. Integrating this module poses a significant challenge as it must seamlessly integrate without compromising the efficiency and speed of the solver.

Numerous strategies can enhance the utility and accuracy of PBM across various applications. For instance, one avenue for improvement involves integrating diverse particle breakage representation schemes within the simulation framework.

3.5 Conclusion

The ongoing construction of a CFD-DEM-PBM framework designed for granular material breakage represents a promising development. This adaptable package offers customization options to address specific problem contexts, accommodating various equations stemming from different models. Furthermore, the framework's capability to generate predictions in real time during simulation execution stands out as a significant advantage. This feature simplifies the design iteration process in engineering applications and facilitates the selection of optimal settings for grinding or milling machinery, ultimately improving efficiency and productivity.

3.6 Best practice guidelines

This section summarizes the various best practices mentioned in the different sections of this chapter. Modeling a granular process involving particle breakage using the CFD-DEM-PBM methodology can be much more comfortable with the following points in mind.

- Identification of breakage mechanism is key to developing or adopting a breakage characterization strategy. Particles in an opposed jet mill break via particle-particle impacts and thus we identify the breakage mechanism as impact breakage. Hence we adopt one of the breakage characterization methods mentioned in the chapter.

- In scenarios where simulating a physical system lacks validating data or the feasibility of sensor data extraction, we resort to constructing or finding a surrogate system. This surrogate system mimics the behavior of the original system while facilitating the validation of underlying physics through visual methods, high-speed cameras, or alternative sensor technologies. This allows one to use the same calibrated settings on the former black-box system hence giving us accurate insights into the system. For instance, consider a setup with a high-speed camera placed above a see-through container. This container contains particles carried by a flow. In simulations using a numerical model, the velocity of the particles relative to the flow may or may not match what is observed. Adjusting the model to make them match typically involves fine-tuning its parameters.
- A PB equation takes only one input from the DEM simulation data. This data is the specific grinding rate, k_i and should ideally contain all the DEM information such as collision frequency, collision energy, effect of mesh movements, influence of CFD parameters on DEM particles, etc. Hence making sure that k_i sincerely communicates all the important aspects of a CFD-DEM simulation with the PBM module is of paramount interest. Hence the value of k_i needs to be rigorously validated against a lot of different comminution machines, literature data and test cases. This is the only way one can increase the trustworthiness of k_i as a proper link between CFD-DEM and PBM.

Chapter 4

CFD-DEM and PBM Upscaling for Wet Stirred Media Mills

4.1 Introduction

Stirred media mills are a type of fine and ultra-fine grinding equipment used in various industries, including mineral processing, chemicals, and pharmaceuticals, to reduce particle sizes down to the micron or even nano-scale [Bilgili and Guner, 2021; Kwade and Schwedes, 2007; Matsanga et al., 2023]. These mills work by agitating a grinding medium, such as beads or balls, together with the material to be ground within a grinding chamber. The high energy and shear forces generated by the stirring action cause the particles to break down.

Key components of a stirred media mill include (see Figure 4.1):

- Grinding chamber: The container where grinding takes place, often made of a wear-resistant material.
- Stirrer/Agitator: Equipped with discs or pins, this rotates and agitates the grinding media and the product material to be ground.
- Grinding media: Small beads or balls made from materials like zirconium oxide, steel, or glass, which are agitated to grind the product particles.
- Feed and discharge system: Mechanisms for introducing the raw material into the mill and for removing the ground product.

The operation of stirred media mills can be either dry or wet:

Dry operation: In dry milling, the material is fed into the grinding chamber without any added

FIGURE 4.1: Representation of the grinding chamber with stirrer of a bench scale wet stirred media mill, MiniCer (Netzsch).

liquid. This method is suitable for materials that are moisture-sensitive or where subsequent drying steps would be problematic. Dry milling can produce fine particles, but it may lead to increased wear on the mill's components and a higher risk of clogging i.e., product flowability is an important factor.

Wet operation: Wet milling involves adding a liquid, usually water or a solvent, to the grinding chamber along with the material to be ground. The liquid can aid in the grinding process by reducing friction and heat, leading to finer particle sizes and a more efficient grinding process. Wet milling is preferred for materials that are not easily ground in dry conditions, and for achieving ultra-fine particle sizes. Ultra-fine particle sizes are relevant, especially in food and pharmaceutical industry to enhance the bio-availability of the consumed product.

The choice between dry and wet milling depends on various factors, including the nature of the material to be ground, the desired particle size, and the specific requirements of the end product. The current work focuses on predicting the grinding performance of Wet-operated Stirred Media Mills (WSMMs).

The key challenge in utilizing stirred media mills effectively lies in determining and optimizing the operational conditions for specific requirements, such as reducing energy consumption and grinding media wear or enhancing throughput for greater productivity. The complexity of this task is heightened by the numerous process variables involved, including the size of the grinding beads, the volume of the beads in the mill (filling degree), the speed of the agitator, the material flow rate, and whether the mill operates continuously or in a batch mode. Additionally, the design features of the mill and the agitator itself can significantly influence performance, making it intricate to pinpoint the optimal combination of parameters for any given application. The

impact of the parameters mentioned can be evaluated through experimental studies [Breitung-Faes and Kwade, 2013; Flach et al., 2018; Kwade and Schwedes, 2007], which helps in identifying the optimal operating conditions. However, this approach demands a significant amount of experimental work to analyze these effects comprehensively. Moreover, the findings obtained from one specific machine setup cannot be directly applied to another setup with different configurations, such as different rotor geometries or bead materials. While Kwade and Schwedes, 2007 have proposed scaling rules to extrapolate the average stress energy from one mill size to another, as utilized by Flach et al., 2017, this scaling method does not provide a precise or qualitative understanding of the stress energy distribution across different scales.

Numerical simulation methods like the Discrete Element Method (DEM) have been utilized to monitor the movement and interactions of grinding beads in dry mills across various designs and scales [de Carvalho and Tavares, 2013; de Carvalho et al., 2021; de Oliveira et al., 2021]. For wet systems, DEM is often coupled with Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) [Beinert et al., 2015; Thon et al., 2022a, 2022b], Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) [Cleary et al., 2006; Ndimande et al., 2019], or the Particle Finite Element Method (PFEM) [Jonsén et al., 2019; Larsson et al., 2020, 2021]. This integration helps in creating a virtual representation of the actual mill environment and in extracting essential data.

Numerical modeling offers an opportunity for virtual process engineering, enabling the acquisition of both qualitative and quantitative data, such as the distribution of stress energy and the positioning of grinding beads within various zones of the mill for grinding and separation [Cabiscol et al., 2021; Fragnière et al., 2021]. The primary challenge of this modeling approach is that it typically does not account for the presence of feed/product particles in the simulations, owing to their large numbers, which would significantly increase simulation time [Berger and Hrenya, 2014; Jajcevic et al., 2013]. The limitation of DEM is its capacity to simulate only a finite number of particles, impacting the duration of the simulation. Despite this, with adequate calibration, the simulations can effectively represent the motion of the grinding media, as well as their relative velocities and stress energy distribution under specific process parameters, thus providing insights into the system dynamics for optimization and establishing best practices.

4.2 Modeling framework

In the context of predicting grinding performance of a WSMM, the aforementioned numerical coupling methodologies alone are not sufficient since, the product particles (in slurry) are not directly simulated, and broken. There are methods one could utilize to include breakage in the simulations such as, bonded particle model [Potyondy and Cundall, 2004], particle replacement model [Tavares and Anderson, 2021], bonded-cell model [Cantor et al., 2017] etc,. However, each of these methods suffer limitations and are not utilized in the current study for obvious

reasons (i.e., exponential increase in particle number if chosen). On the other hand, Population Balance Modeling (PBM), is one such modeling strategies which is widely utilized in prediction of grinding performance [de Carvalho et al., 2023; Tavares, 2017; Vogel and Peukert, 2005]. It is computationally inexpensive (compared to DEM or CFD) but requires additional information to define the kernel coefficients which drive the desired phenomena (breakage in this context). There are quite a few implementations of PBM kernels which include the inputs from (CFD-) DEM derived data [Chen et al., 2020; de Carvalho et al., 2023].

Here, a framework to establish necessary simulations (CFD-DEM) to model WSMMs shall be explained (along with the assumptions, and modeling considerations). Methods on how to utilize (CFD-) DEM derived data in PBM will be elaborated using the models from literature. Figure 4.2, shows a simple schematic of the approach being followed in the current work. As discussed earlier, the population balance model requires additional information to assume the kernel coefficients. In the context of pure breakage, the required kernels are breakage rate (disappearance) and breakage distribution (appearance) (see Figure 4.2), which define the mass loss in each particle class i , and the transfer of mass from class j to class i , respectively.

FIGURE 4.2: Schematic of modeling framework for wet stirred media mills.

There are several definitions of these kernel functions in literature, based on the physical (breakage) phenomena. To mention a few, Vogel and Peukert, 2005 have their kernel definitions based on the impact breakage, and Tavares, 2017 has considered the particle compression in between two rigid bodies. However, along with the material (breakage) characteristics, such kernels need information about the machine behavior (at its operating settings), to define the breakage rate. Experimentally, it is not possible to extract the quantitative information from the machine at different operating settings, therefore numerical methods like DEM are used to get such information. But, the numerical modeling should be aided with proper calibration to

accurately represent the system. In the current work, coupled CFD-DEM modeling shall be used due to the fact that it is a multiphase system and requires additional hydrodynamic forces on the particles.

4.3 Methodology

This section elaborates and gives necessary discussion on the components (Figure 4.2) required to establish the modeling of WSMMs. The components include coupled CFD-DEM simulations, and a population balance model.

Note that, most of the content in the model formulation of mill simulations and the corresponding results are the work of Tanneru et al., 2024 (one of the author of this document). The content, and the results shall be reproduced directly or with necessary changes.

4.3.1 Coupled CFD-DEM modeling of wet stirred media mill

Unresolved CFD-DEM coupling [Kloss et al., 2012] gives a continuous description of the fluid phase, coarser than that of the particulate scale, using the Volume-Averaged Navier Stokes (VANS) equations while the particulate phase is modeled using the Discrete Element Method (DEM), which tracks the motion of discrete entities (particulate phase). The CFD and DEM are operated independently with their respective governing equations, but are coupled at regular intervals (usually multiple DEM time steps for a single CFD time step). The governing equations of the adopted models are described below:

DEM formulation

In the present work, the particle motion (translational and rotational) is solved using an academic adaptation of the open-source DEM code, LIGGGHTS [Kloss et al., 2012].

According to Newton's second law, the translational (\mathbf{v}_i) and rotational ($\boldsymbol{\omega}_i$) motions of a particle i can be described using the following equations:

$$m_i \frac{d\mathbf{v}_i}{dt} = \sum_j \mathbf{f}_{c,ij} + \sum_k \mathbf{f}_{nc,ik} + \mathbf{f}_{pf,i} + \mathbf{f}_{g,i} \quad (4.1)$$

$$I_i \frac{d\boldsymbol{\omega}_i}{dt} = \sum_j (\mathbf{M}_{t,ij} + \mathbf{M}_{r,ij}) \quad (4.2)$$

where m_i represents the mass of particle i , I_i is its moment of inertia, $\mathbf{f}_{c,ij}$ denotes the contact force(s) between particle i and particle j , $\mathbf{f}_{nc,ik}$ represents the non-contact forces between particle i and particle k , $\mathbf{f}_{pf,i}$ is the particle–fluid interaction forces, $\mathbf{f}_{g,i}$ signifies a body force like gravity. $M_{t,ij}$ and $M_{r,ij}$ are the tangential and rolling moments acting on particle i and particle j , respectively. In this work, a lubrication force is adopted as a non-contact force, while the other non-contact forces, such as the electrostatic or van der Waals forces, are not considered, as they are orders of magnitude smaller than the hydrodynamic or contact forces for the particles (grinding beads) considered. The expression for the particle–fluid interaction force depends on the interactions considered (drag, lift, etc.). Further, the contact force between two particles $\mathbf{f}_{c,ij}$ can be split into two components i.e., normal ($\mathbf{f}_{cn,ij}$) and tangential ($\mathbf{f}_{ct,ij}$) [Zhu et al., 2007].

A contact model based on the Hertz theory for the normal forces [Hertz, 1881; Johnson, 1989], and the Mindlin model (with no-slip) [Mindlin and Deresiewicz, 1953; Mindlin, 1949] for the tangential forces are chosen and a constant directional torque was chosen as the rolling resistance model [Ai et al., 2011].

A non-contact model in the form of lubrication forces [Mewis and Wagner, 2012] are introduced in the present frame work. The inclusion of these forces are mainly because of the fact that, beads immersed in a viscous fluid affect each other via lubrication forces (also, known as fluid displacement forces). These are relevant when two beads are in close proximity with each other and the forces originate from the squeeze out or suck in of the fluid in between the particle surfaces.

This effect of lubrication forces is considered for similar systems in the literature [Beinert et al., 2012; Cabiscol et al., 2021]. In the present work, the lubrication forces are added in the DEM as a non-contact force model to emulate the near-particle hydrodynamic interactions. They are added in DEM as the fluid solver doesn't provide enough resolution to capture the particle interface(s). In the current work, a lubrication force model described by Kroupa et al., 2016 is adopted. The expressions were derived with an assumption that the flow between the two approaching bodies is in the Stokes' limit.

A big issue to compute the lubrication forces is that when the collision velocity of beads $v \rightarrow 0$ and when the surface distance between the beads $h \rightarrow 0$, the force calculation leads to $0 \cdot \infty$ (since the lubrication force $F_{lub} \propto v$, and $F_{lub} \propto \frac{1}{h}$). To overcome this divergent behavior of the lubrication forces, a correction factor f^* , suggested by Vinogradova, 1995, was adopted in Kroupa et al., 2016. However, in the present work the lubrication forces are only evaluated until a specified cut-off distance d_{cut} after which they are not computed and are not taken into account i.e., the lubrication forces are only prevalent at $d_{cut} \leq h < d_{gb}$, where h is the surface distance between the mono-disperse beads i and j . In this case, the correction factor f^* is not used.

CFD and CFD-DEM coupling formulation

The incompressible Volume-Averaged Navier Stokes (VANS) equations considered in this work are adopted from the work of Zhou et al., 2010. The equations adopted are described as set II in Zhou et al., 2010, which are given as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \varepsilon_f}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\varepsilon_f \mathbf{u}) = 0 \quad (4.3)$$

$$\frac{\partial (\rho_f \varepsilon_f \mathbf{u})}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_f \varepsilon_f \mathbf{u} \mathbf{u}) = -\varepsilon_f \nabla p + \varepsilon_f \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau} + \rho_f \varepsilon_f \mathbf{g} - \mathbf{F}_{pf} \quad (4.4)$$

where ε_f is the void fraction, ρ_f is the fluid density, \mathbf{u} is the velocity, \mathbf{g} is the gravity, and p is the pressure. The viscous tensor $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ is given as:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = \mu_f \left((\nabla \mathbf{u}) + (\nabla \mathbf{u})^T - \frac{2}{3} (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}) \boldsymbol{\delta}_k \right) \quad (4.5)$$

where μ_f is the dynamic viscosity and $\boldsymbol{\delta}_k$ is the identity tensor.

In equation 4.4, the term \mathbf{F}_{pf} is the momentum exchange term from beads to the fluid. It is given as:

$$\mathbf{F}_{pf} = \frac{1}{\Delta V} \sum_i^{n_p} \mathbf{f}_{pf,i} - \mathbf{f}_{\nabla p,i} - \mathbf{f}_{\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau},i} - \mathbf{f}_{Ar,i} \quad (4.6)$$

where,

$$\mathbf{f}_{pf,i} = \mathbf{f}_{d,i} + \mathbf{f}_{\nabla p,i} + \mathbf{f}_{\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau},i} + \mathbf{f}_{Ar,i} + \mathbf{f}_{vm,i} + \mathbf{f}_{B,i} + \mathbf{f}_{Saff,i} + \mathbf{f}_{Mag,i} \quad (4.7)$$

where n_p is the number of particles, ΔV is the volume of the cell in which a particle i is present and $\mathbf{f}_{pf,i}$ is the sum of all fluid-solid interaction forces that involve particle i . This term can be sub-divided into several contributions such as, drag $\mathbf{f}_{d,i}$, pressure gradient $\mathbf{f}_{\nabla p,i}$, shear or viscous stress $\mathbf{f}_{\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau},i}$, Archimedes or buoyant force $\mathbf{f}_{Ar,i}$, virtual mass $\mathbf{f}_{vm,i}$, Basset force $\mathbf{f}_{B,i}$, Saffman lift force $\mathbf{f}_{Saff,i}$, and Magnus lift force $\mathbf{f}_{Mag,i}$. The equations 4.3 and 4.4 are solved using a Pressure Implicit with Splitting of Operators (PISO) scheme [Issa, 1986].

In this work, only the drag, pressure gradient, viscous (shear), and Archimedes forces are taken into account and all other force calculations in equation 4.7 are ignored, as they are not relevant for the current case. The expressions for the pressure gradient, viscous (shear) can be found in Zhu et al., 2007. Koch-Hill drag model, which calculates the particle based drag force given by

Koch and Hill, 2001 (as described by Van Buijtenen et al., 2011) is adopted in this work, which was tested and used in the modeling applications of wet stirred media mills [Beinert et al., 2018; Fragnière et al., 2021].

Additional numerical adaptations such as, 'divided' approach [Kloss et al., 2012], and 'diffusive smoothing' [Pirker et al., 2011], to stabilize the fields (like, void fraction, and momentum exchange) are adopted. The implementations are existing in the adopted CFDEM framework [Goniva et al., 2012; Kloss et al., 2012]. The details for this choice in the current work are further elaborated in Tanneru et al., 2024.

Stirrer/agitator motion in CFD

There are several methodologies to realize the motion of rotating bodies in CFD. The methodologies include the sliding mesh (SM), multiple reference frame (MRF) and the single rotating frame (SRF). However, each of these methodologies suffer from limitations in terms of the type of geometries that they can handle and their capability to solve steady or unsteady problems [Van den Akker, 2006]. On the other hand, immersed boundary (IB) and fictitious domain (FD) approaches serve as alternatives for the aforementioned methods, as they can handle complex geometries and can be easily implemented in parallel to achieve computational efficiency. Moreover, they can be used in the applications with multiple impellers and situations with overlapping swept volumes and can handle 6 degrees of freedom of geometry movement.

In the present work, the stirrer movement is emulated using a semi-implicit immersed boundary (IB) approach, implemented within pressure implicit with splitting of operators (PISO) scheme, termed as PISO-IB that was introduced by Blais et al., 2016a. The approach was then extended to implement the coupling of DEM (with CFD) to model the solid-liquid mixing [Blais et al., 2016b]. This method was integrated within the CFDEM framework [Goniva et al., 2012; Kloss et al., 2012], and it can be used with unstructured meshes. It requires a surface mesh of a moving object to describe its motion within the computational domain and can be used with static mesh or dynamic mesh refinement.

The basic idea of the PISO-IB approach is to determine the moving geometry on the computational domain using a cell center and vertex flagging method. The surface mesh, i.e., an STL file in this case, is projected onto the finite volume (FV) mesh by generating a Boolean list that indicates which cell centers and vertices of the FV mesh intersect with the given surface mesh. Figure 4.3 illustrates the cell center and vertex detection technique, that creates two lists called fluid and solid nodes (in white and gray regions respectively). Thereby a solid fraction for each cell i is generated. Further details about the numerical implementation of the underlying schemes and method validation for single-phase mixing can be found in Blais et al., 2016a.

FIGURE 4.3: A 2D illustration of the cell center and vertex flagging method.

Simulation setup and post-processing

The geometry of a bench-scale wet-operated stirred media mill, Minicer from Netzsch is chosen for the current work. The STL files are generated using Autodesk Inventor 2022 (see Figure 4.1). The simulations were setup with the aforementioned modeling considerations (in Sections 4.3.1 & 4.3.1). Each simulation case is implemented in three stages: initialize, stabilize, and run. The initialization step signifies, that the simulation domain is initialized with a predetermined number of particles calculated using the equation 4.8. This calculation is based on the active volume for bead filling V_{act} , the mill filling degree ϕ , the porosity α , and the diameter of the grinding beads d_{gb} . The number is then rounded to the nearest integer value. The pore fraction value is assumed to be 0.41, which leads to a packing density factor of 0.59, representing loose random packing of spheres. During the particle insertion, the stirrer is rotated for one rotation to disperse the particles in the computational domain. After the particle insertion into the domain, the simulation is restarted (with the user-defined rotation speed) from the previous state and is coupled with CFD via two-way coupling, i.e., the exchange of forces between particles to fluid and fluid to particles takes place. This step is continued for two more stirrer rotations until the system is assumed to be stabilized (when the total kinetic energy of the particles in the system is relatively constant, as shown in Figure 4.4). Then, the system is restarted again for one more stirrer rotation to collect the necessary data for post-processing.

$$N_{gb} = \frac{V_{act}\phi(1-\alpha)}{\frac{\pi}{6}d_{gb}^3} \quad (4.8)$$

FIGURE 4.4: Total kinetic energy of the particles with respect to simulation run-time. Purple and green trends indicate the stable (2 rotations), and run (1 rotation) steps, respectively. **Case:** $1100 \mu\text{m}$ beads at 6.18 m/s , with 80% bead filling [Tanneru et al., 2024].

All of the properties and parameters used in this study are tabulated in Table 4.1. Note that the parameters of both particle-particle and particle-wall interactions are assumed same, as it is the same material (Zirconium Oxide - ZrO_2). The Young's modulus of the material is reduced by 100 orders of magnitude for computational feasibility [Lommen et al., 2014]. As described in Section 4.3.1, a (lower) cut-off distance was chosen to inhibit the lubrication force.

Property	Symbol	Units	Value
Young's modulus	Y	GPa	1
Density (beads)	ρ_{gb}	$\frac{kg}{m^3}$	6050
Poisson's ratio	ν	—	0.31
Coefficient of restitution	e	—	0.92
Coefficient of static friction	μ_s	—	0.15
Coefficient of rolling friction	μ_r	—	0.01
Cut-off distance	d_{cut}	m	$0.05 d_{gb}$
Density (water)	ρ_f	$\frac{kg}{m^3}$	998.2
Viscosity (water)	η_f	$mPa s$	1.0016
Time step (DEM)	Δt_{DEM}	s	1×10^{-6}
Time step (CFD)	Δt_{CFD}	s	1×10^{-6}
Coupling interval	—	—	10

TABLE 4.1: Material properties and parameters used in the coupled CFD-DEM simulations.

The finite volume grid for CFD calculations is generated using *blockMesh* and *snappyHexMesh* utilities of OpenFOAM-6. The mesh is generated such that most of the cells are hexahedrons with an average non-orthogonality of 13° . To be conservative, the CFD mesh is chosen such that the average edge length of the cells in the domain are 2.5 to 3.0 times the particle diameter, i.e., $\Delta x \leq 2.5 - 3.0d_{gb}$ [Z. Wang and Liu, 2021]. A smoothing length, $\lambda = 3d_{gb}$ is chosen to account for the field smothering of cells with smaller edge lengths. The mesh was kept constant for all the simulation cases. The $k - \varepsilon$ turbulence model was chosen to account for fluid turbulence.

The time step of DEM is chosen as a fraction of the Rayleigh time step criterion and for the CFD time-step (with an implicit scheme for viscous term of the VANS equations), followed the Courant-Friedrich-Lewy (CFL) [Ferziger et al., 2019] criterion i.e., it was ensured that this value never exceeds 0.9, and it was indeed one of the stopping criteria for all simulation cases.

The extracted results from the simulations include the stress energy and their frequency, since these are the important metrics in a bead mill [Kwade, 2003; Kwade and Schwedes, 2007], at different operation settings. The established relations for stress energy and stress frequency calculation are given in equations 4.9 and 4.10, respectively.

$$SE_{gb} \propto d_{gb}^3 \cdot \rho_{gb} \cdot v_t^2 \quad (4.9)$$

Here, SE_{gb} is a measure of the maximum stress energy in the mill (that might be different to the mean stress energy in the system (\overline{SE}_{gb}), because of different stress energies of grinding beads in the system due to their spatial relative velocity distribution). d_{gb} is the diameter of the grinding beads, ρ_{gb} is their density, and v_t is the tip speed of the stirrer, calculated using equation 4.11, with n the stirrer rotation speed and R_{tip} representing the distance from the center of rotation of the stirrer to its tip.

$$SF = \frac{N_c}{t} \propto n \cdot N_{gb} \quad (4.10)$$

Here, $\frac{N_c}{t}$ is the number of contacts per unit time, and N_{gb} is the number of grinding beads in the system given by equation 4.8.

$$v_t = 2\pi n R_{tip} \quad (4.11)$$

In this work, this information is evaluated using the collisional (DEM) kinetic energies in the system i.e., is the maximum transferable energy, calculated at the first contact of the two colliding entities [Beinert et al., 2015] (bead-bead or bead-wall) in the system (see equation 4.12).

$$SE_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot m^* \cdot v_{rel}^2 \quad (4.12)$$

Here, SE_{ij} is the stress energy of a collision event involving the entities i and j , m^* is the equivalent mass of the entities involved in a collision (i.e., $\frac{1}{m^*} = \frac{1}{m_1} + \frac{1}{m_2}$, with m_1 , m_2 being the masses of two entities in a collision; $m_1 = m_2 = m_{gb}$ for a bead-bead collision and $m_1 = m_{gb}$, $m_2 = \infty$ for a bead-wall collision). v_{rel} is the relative velocity of two colliding entities.

FIGURE 4.5: Possible ideal contact types and the corresponding directions of translational and rotational velocities (according to Beinert et al., 2015). The subscripts t, n, r, and s represent the translational, normal, rolling and shearing modes respectively.

The equation 4.12 is evaluated as a summation of the energies from all contact modes, as shown in Figure 4.5. The corresponding equation for summation of the energies across the contact modes is given in equation 4.13. For all stress energy distributions, every decade is logarithmic equally spaced into 100 intervals, i.e., a total of 2000 intervals with the lowest limit translating to $10^{-20} J$.

$$SE_{total} = m^* \left[\frac{1}{2} (\vec{v}_{n,rel})^2 + \frac{1}{5} r^2 (\vec{\omega}_{n,rel})^2 + \frac{1}{2} (\vec{v}_{s_1} - \vec{v}_{s_2})^2 + \frac{1}{5} r^2 (\vec{\omega}_{s_1} - \vec{\omega}_{s_2})^2 + \frac{1}{2} (\vec{v}_{r_1} + \vec{v}_{r_2})^2 + \frac{1}{5} r^2 (\vec{\omega}_{r_1} + \vec{\omega}_{r_2})^2 \right] \quad (4.13)$$

where the \vec{v} and $\vec{\omega}$ indicate the translational and rotational velocity vectors respectively. The subscripts n , s , and r represent the normal, shearing and rolling modes, respectively (as illustrated in Figure 4.5).

4.3.2 Model formulation for PBM approach

As discussed earlier, a PBM approach is adopted to predict the grinding of a stirred media mill. The (coupled CFD-DEM) simulations here are used to derive the machine function i.e., machine performance at various operation settings. Two modeling approaches of interest in the literature, that are applicable to fine grinding applications are: impact/collision based model [Vogel and Peukert, 2005], and UFRJ mechanistic model [Tavares, 2017]. The PBM for stirred media mill modeling (described in UFRJ model) is described in equation 4.14.

$$\frac{dw_i(t)}{dt} = \frac{1}{M} \left(w_i(t) + \sum_{k=1}^{N_k} \omega_k \left[-D_{ik}^b(t) - D_{ik}^s(t) + A_{ik}^b(t) + A_{ik}^s(t) \right] \right) \quad (4.14)$$

where M is the mill hold-up, w_i is the mass fraction of particles contained in size class i in the mill at time t . Here, w_i is being evolved with respect to the (grinding) time. ω_k is the frequency of collision events of class k , D_{ik} is the disappearance term and A_{ik} is the appearance term, b is the subscript indicating that the term refers to volumetric (body) breakage, s is the subscript indicating that the term refers to surface breakage. N_k is the number of collision classes in the mill. Both the disappearance and appearance terms of the particles are described in Table 4.2.

Term	Equation
$D_{ik}^b(t)$	$= w_i(t) \int_0^\infty m_{i,k}^*(E) p_k(E) \int_0^1 [1 - b_{ii}(eE)] F_i(eE, t) p_{i,k}(e) dedE$
$D_{ik}^s(t)$	$= w_i(t) \kappa_i \int_0^\infty m_{i,k}^*(E) p_k(E) \int_0^1 [1 - F_i(eE, t)] p_{i,k}(e) dedE$
$A_{ik}^b(t)$	$= \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} w_j(t) \int_0^\infty m_{j,k}^*(E) p_k(E) \int_0^1 b_{ij}(eE, t) F_j(eE, t) p_{j,k}(e) dedE$
$A_{ik}^s(t)$	$= \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} w_j(t) \kappa_j \int_0^\infty m_{j,k}^*(E) p_k(E) \int_0^1 s_{ij}(eE, t) [1 - F_j(eE, t)] p_{j,k}(e) dedE$

TABLE 4.2: Description of the disappearance and appearance terms in equation 4.14 (refer de Carvalho et al., 2023 for further details).

As all the particles dispersed in the fluid (inside the mill) undergo stressing, it is important to identify the stressed amount of particles here. The PBM model accounts this in the term $m_{i,k}^*$, which describes the amount of mass in particle class i , captured in collision class k . The parameter effect and modeling considerations are described in Section 4.3.3. The model in Table 4.2 also considers the stressing energy split if more than a single particle is captured in a stressing event, given by $p_{i,k}(e)$. $P_k(E)$ represents the distribution of stressing energies of magnitude E in the mill for the collision class k . $b_{ij}(eE)$ is the body breakage distribution function in density form, which also depends on the magnitude of each stressing energy and is described using the incomplete beta function [de Carvalho and Tavares, 2013].

In short, to model the wet stirred media mills using PBM, one should have the following information:

- The description of machine and material functions, obtained from the calibrated CFD-DEM simulations, and experimental analysis, respectively.
- The breakage probability which is a combination of machine and material functions.
- Description captured mass for the given conditions.
- A function describing the breakage distribution i.e., progeny size distribution after breakage.

4.3.3 Coupled CFD-DEM simulations for capture probability

The need for a capture probability assessment comes from the assumption that was made to model the mill simulations i.e., the simulations don't include the motion, and breakage of product particles within them. This leads to a question about the actual mass of the product particle in the system that has actually been stressed. And, only the stressed mass in a given time shall undergo breakage. The main parameters that influence/drive this capture probability are: solids concentration (amount of product particles dispersed in fluid), size (and particle size distribution) of the product particles, size of the grinding beads, and the approach velocity. The parameters also include the density of bead & product particles, and the fluid properties in which the product particles are suspended.

The influence of the aforementioned parameters on the captured mass are difficult to determine experimentally. There are limited experimental investigations which analysed this phenomenon. Barrios et al., 2011 have used drop wright tests on unconfined particle beds to describe the volume of material captured in each stressing event, and the uneven distribution of the stressing energy among particles contained in the bed. Mende, 2006 has made an experimental setup where the approaching grinding beads are represented using a sphere and a fixed semi-sphere. It was identified that the capturing of product particles increases when the volume fraction was increased.

In the current study a resolved CFD-DEM modeling approach [Goniva et al., 2012; Kloss et al., 2012] is employed as a first try to study the parameter influence. The following method and findings are evaluated in a master's thesis study [Choi and Tanneru, 2023].

Simulation setup and post-processing

The simulation setup as shown in Figure 4.6 is established. The initial position of the grinding media is kept such that the distance between their surfaces is equal to the bead diameter

d_i . Mono-disperse product particles with diameter d_j are generated in between the grinding beads using a representative cube volume (with a length $l = d_i$). The number of product particles generated depends on the particle volume concentration, which depends on the solids concentration. Equations 4.15 & 4.16 used to evaluate the volume concentration of particles that need to be generated. Where, c_v , and c_m are the volume and solids concentrations, respectively. ρ_l , ρ_s , and ρ_m are the liquid, solid (product particle) and mixture densities, respectively. After all the particles along with grinding beads are generated, the grinding beads start to move towards each other with a specified relative velocity v_{rel} . The simulation settings are tabulated in Tables 4.3 & 4.4 and the evaluated cases are tabulated in Table 4.5.

FIGURE 4.6: Simulation setup of grinding beads along with product particles.

$$c_v = c_m \times \frac{\rho_m}{\rho_s} \quad (4.15)$$

$$\rho_m = \frac{1}{\frac{c_m}{\rho_s} + \frac{1-c_m}{\rho_l}} \quad (4.16)$$

	Density [kg/m^3]	Young's modulus [GPa]	Poisson's ratio [-]
Grinding bead	6067	210	0.31
Product particle	2650	0.5225	0.25
Liquid	998.2	-	-

TABLE 4.3: Physical properties of the material.

	Coefficient of restitution	Static friction coefficient	Rolling resistance coefficient
Bead \leftrightarrow Bead	0.92	0.15	0.01
Bead \leftrightarrow Product	0.557	0.61	0.07
Product \leftrightarrow Product	0.208	0.77	0.1

TABLE 4.4: Interaction properties of the material.

Case	d_i [mm]	d_j [μm]	c_m [-]	c_v [-]	v_{rel} [m/s]
1	1.0	70	0.2	0.086	0.01
2	1.0	70	0.2	0.086	0.025
3	1.0	70	0.2	0.086	0.0025
4	1.0	70	0.25	0.111	0.01
..
39	1.5	80	0.2	0.086	0.025
40	1.5	80	0.2	0.086	0.0025
..
78	2.0	100	0.25	0.111	0.0025
79	2.0	100	0.3	0.138	0.01
80	2.0	100	0.3	0.138	0.025
81	2.0	100	0.3	0.138	0.0025

TABLE 4.5: Evaluated CFD-DEM simulation cases for the capture probability assessment.

Each case in Table 4.5 is executed and the information about the particles collided are extracted using the particle ID's. Here, the grinding beads are given ID's 1 and 2 respectively, and the product particles are numbered starting from 3. Each collision event is tracked with the colliding particle ID's, the time, etc. All of the events are stored in a text file, which is then filtered to only get the necessary information for further analysis i.e., the time-step and colliding particle ID's (see Figure 4.7). The (product) particle is said to be captured if the same particle has a simultaneous collision instance with both the grinding beads i.e., at the same time-step.

4.4 Results

4.4.1 Coupled CFD-DEM simulations of wet stirred media mill

DEM Vs coupled CFD-DEM

To identify the need for the coupling of the DEM with CFD, and the necessity for the inclusion of the lubrication, the following analysis is implemented comparing different approaches. Figure 4.8 illustrates the comparisons of results from different DEM and coupled CFD-DEM simulations. The results indicate a significant difference in stress energy distribution when DEM only and coupled CFD-DEM are considered (see Figures 4.8b & 4.8d). This indicates that the system is well- agitated in case of couple CFD-DEM simulations compared to DEM only. The effect of lubrication has it's effect on both DEM only (with lubrication, see Figure 4.8a), and coupled CFD-DEM (see Figure 4.8c) cases. The comparisons show that the effect of lubrication is not significant for low viscous fluids like water but are important to consider for moderate to high viscous fluids. It can be observed in Figure 4.8b that, the cases with different fluid properties are almost identical for the stress frequency values, with a subtle difference in the overall distribution

FIGURE 4.7: Workflow to post-process and assess the captured particles between the grinding beads.

(shifted to right). One might expect that there will be a significant difference in the stress energy distributions for such change in fluid properties.

Effect of operating parameters

The effect of operating parameters such as the bead diameter, stirrer tip speed, and the bead filling degree are analysed using the system characteristics like the mean stress energy and the stress frequency (for a given combination of parameter set). The trends of these system characteristics can be seen in Figures 4.9a & 4.9b. The trends of these results comply with the relations described in the equations 4.9 and 4.10. A non-linear regression analysis is performed on the data obtained from the simulations. The regression analysis showed that, $\overline{SE}_{gb} \propto d_{gb}^{4.27}$, and $\overline{SE}_{gb} \propto v_t^{1.92}$. This deviation for the grinding bead diameter dependency was also observed in the work of Beinert et al., 2015. The dependency of stress frequency are obtained as, $SF \propto N_{gb}^{1.27}$, and $SF \propto n^{0.31}$. This dependency of stress frequency was not comparable to the regression

FIGURE 4.8: Stress energy distributions showcasing the system behavior at various model considerations. (A) DEM only, (B) DEM and coupled CFD-DEM comparison without lubrication effect, (C) Coupled CFD-DEM comparison with and without lubrication effect, (D) DEM and coupled CFD-DEM comparison. All the cases were setup with the stirrer tip speed of 9.27 m/s, bead diameter of 1100 μ m, and a filling degree of 0.8 ($N_{gb} = 135455$) [taken from Tanneru et al., 2024].

coefficients in Beinert et al., 2015 but, it can be seen that the stress frequency dependency on the stirrer speed is reduced, both in the current study and in the study of Beinert et al., 2015 (who used a mill of different scale and different stirrer configuration). This dependency reduction on the stirrer speed could be inferred as an effect of change in fluid flow regime, where the stress frequency is impacted by the fluid flow rather than the stirrer speed directly.

Effect of fluid properties

To analyse the effect of the fluid properties on the system behaviour an analysis using the water-glycerol mixture properties from the literature [Cheng, 2008; Volk and Kähler, 2018] are

FIGURE 4.9: Comparison of the system behavior at different operating conditions i.e., stirrer tip speed, bead diameter, filling degree. (A) Comparison of mean stress energy of the system, (B) Comparison of stress frequency of the system [taken from Tanneru et al., 2024].

used, as described in Table 4.6. The simulations for this analysis are carried out with a filling degree of 0.7 and a stirrer tip speed of 6.18 m/s using $1100 \mu\text{m}$ beads. Figure 4.10a shows the entire stress energy distribution of different mixtures. It can be seen that the distribution has significant change when the percentage of Glycerol is the highest. This shows that the change in fluid properties will indeed effect the system dynamics (especially for medium to high viscosities). The change in the stress frequency due to the fluid properties (indicated by the percentage of glycerol present in water by volume) is depicted in Figure 4.10b.

% of Water, Glycerol [v/v]	Viscosity [mPa s]	Density [$\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$]
100, 0	1.0016	998.2
75, 25	2.094	1069.5
50, 50	6.8559	1139.3
25, 75	41.295	1202.4

TABLE 4.6: Water, and Water + Glycerol properties [Cheng, 2008; Volk and Kähler, 2018] used in the coupled CFD-DEM simulations.

4.4.2 Coupled CFD-DEM simulations for capture probability

Effect of bead particle size

Figure 4.11, shows the dependence of bead size on the captured particles. It can be seen that when the bead size is increased from 1 mm to 2 mm , the overall number of particles (shaded

FIGURE 4.10: Effect of fluid properties i.e, fluid viscosity and density. (A) Stress energy distributions from simulations with different fluid properties, according to Table 4.6, (B) Fluid properties effect on the mean stress energy (left) and stress frequency (right). All cases are at 0.7 filling degree, stirrer tip speed of 6.18 m/s with $1100\ \mu\text{m}$ beads [taken from Tanneru et al., 2024].

squares) captured has increased. It could be interpreted that when the bead size (diameter) is increased, the volume of the capture region is increased, which increases the capture probability.

Effect of product particle size

Figure 4.12, shows the dependence of product particle size on the captured particles. It can be seen that when the product particle size is increased from $70\ \mu\text{m}$ to $100\ \mu\text{m}$, the overall number of particles (shaded squares) captured has increased. It could be interpreted that the product particles with bigger size are less affected by the fluid flow i.e., the reaction time of bigger particles is lower. This minimizes the movement of the product particles outside the capture zone and hence the increase in capture probability.

Effect of solids concentration

Figure 4.13, shows the dependence of the solids concentration of the product particles on the captured particles. It can be seen that when the solids concentration is increased from 0.2 to 0.3, the overall number of particles (shaded squares) captured has decreased. This is because of the fact that the current analysis only considers the particles that are captured directly in between the beads and doesn't consider the particle capture in bed.

FIGURE 4.11: Heat-map of the number of product particles captured with respect to the bead size [Choi and Tanneru, 2023].

FIGURE 4.12: Heat-map of the number of product particles captured with respect to the product particle size [Choi and Tanneru, 2023].

FIGURE 4.13: Heat-map of the number of product particles captured with respect to the solids concentration [Choi and Tanneru, 2023].

4.4.3 Material characterization

Information about the material breakage behavior is one of the key things that is required to estimate the breakage dynamics in a wet stirred media mill using PBM models. It was understood from the previous studies that the breakage of a given particle is both size and energy (applied) dependent [Tavares, 2022] i.e., there exists a minimum threshold (range) where a given particle starts to deform and exhibit noticeable breakage and such threshold is also particle size dependent. This stands true in case of most of the mineral ores which are brittle in nature. Also, the information about the progeny distribution with respect to an applied energy (ζ threshold energy) is needed to characterize the material's breakage pattern, which enables the reconstruction of the product particle size distribution in the PBM. This is the so-called "Breakage Function".

Devices like impact load cells and drop weight testers are typically used to obtain such information [Tavares, 2022]. But, the breakage characterization of small particles (≤ 100 μm) is still a challenge to this day. A breakage tester [Böttcher et al., 2021] was developed to characterize the breakage of particles in lower micron range. An alternative to this is the usage of the centrifugal pin mill (see Figure 4.14) where the particles are stressed by the fast rotating pins. The applied energy can be maintained using the rotation speed of the pins. An assumption in

this approach is that the particles are stressed at least and only once after which they leave the system. Figures 4.15 & 4.16 show the resulting breakage probabilities and progeny distributions for a certain particle class (315-400 μm) of a calcium carbonate ore, obtained from the breakage characterization experiments in the centrifugal mill.

FIGURE 4.14: DEM simulation snap of the centrifugal mill - ZM200 (with pins) from Retsch.

FIGURE 4.15: Breakage probabilities of the CaCO_3 particles (315-400 μm) stressed in the centrifugal mill at different specific energies.

FIGURE 4.16: Progeny distributions of the $CaCO_3$ particles (315-400 μm) stressed in the centrifugal mill at different specific energies.

4.4.4 Population balance modeling

The PBM formulation in the current context is a work under progress and should be possible to apply (for a real case scenario) once the calibration of simulations is established.

4.5 Challenges and outlook

Calibration strategy

Grinding in wet stirred media mills involves a continuous change in particle size distribution of particles (dispersed in slurry). This change in PSD leads to a change in slurry behavior. Other than this, the solids concentration and the type of particles also plays an important role in describing the bulk behavior (in a mill). Conventionally, the fluid properties like viscosity are characterised using a rheometer which provides a torque response on the couette, for the applied shear rate on the fluid. However, the lab scale rheometers can only emulate low shear rates, compared to the shear rates in the mill. Therefore, it is necessary to assess the fluid behavior at such shear rates where the mill is operated. In this work, we plan to use a stirred tank device as illustrated in Figure 4.17, that could provide the desired (high) shear rates. Various fluids shall be tested for the effect of solids concentration, particle size, particle size distribution, and specific gravity (with respect to the dispersing liquid). The idea is to extract corresponding torque (using a torque feedback unit) for an applied shear rate (speed of the agitator). The torques obtained could be than compared to the simulation torque for a specific fluid viscosity (and density) setting.

FIGURE 4.17: Tank equipped with stirrer and motor (with torque feedback unit).

Capture probability

The need of capture probability is detailed in Section 4.3.3 and the different parameter influence on capture probability is highlighted in Section 4.4.2. This was investigated with an assumption that a single particle must be in contact with both the grinding beads simultaneously. This however doesn't account for the scenarios with breakage, direction of the grinding bead approach, and the influence of the other grinding beads (in a real mill). To account for particle breakage, a particle replacement model can be used. But, it needs a pre-established breakage threshold of product particles. Further work is needed to improve the capture probability with aforementioned phenomena.

Population balance modeling

As described in Section 4.3.2, PBM is a labyrinth that includes a lot of functions and sub-functions that should be tested and established for the current case. This is a work in progress at this point.

4.6 Conclusion

In this chapter, a framework for a CFD-DEM based PBM approach is proposed in the context of grinding prediction in wet stirred media mills. The motivation for the necessity of coupled CFD-DEM simulations is established. Modeling considerations, assumptions, and the simulation setup for the coupled CFD-DEM simulations are explained. An immersed boundary methodology is chosen to emulate the stirrer rotation in CFD. The advantage of the IB method is that it can be used to emulate the motion of geometries with arbitrary designs. The results of the mill simulations indicate that the lubrication forces are essential in an unresolved CFD-DEM coupling approach, especially in case of medium to high viscous fluids.

PBM in this case is a simple yet complex equation, which requires the inclusion of several sub-models and assumptions to establish it completely. One of which is the evaluation of the mass captured in each particle size class. The capture probability assessment using coupled CFD-DEM analysis provided key initial insights but should be improved to include the phenomena like breakage, and neighbour effect on the capture rate. The input data for PBM from the mill simulations should come from the calibrated cases i.e., it is important to establish calibrated simulations. The breakage rate of PBM is a combination of material breakage threshold, and the breakage/collision energy provided by the machine. This could be calculated once the material is characterised. A breakage distribution function in the PBM, which describes the progeny size distribution, should also be established.

4.7 Best practice guidelines

- Simulations of wet stirred media mills even with the assumption of virtual product particles is still a computationally expensive study. It is important to identify the steady-state of the system, which in this work was assumed with the calculation of the total kinetic energy of particles after two stirrer rotations.
- As an initial analysis in the current work, the material properties are adjusted to achieve a compromise on the simulation run-time. However, a sensitivity analysis of the DEM proved that it will affect the system dynamics. Therefore, it is important to choose right parameters that could represent the operating state of the system. This should be executed with a calibration and validation strategy.
- It is evident that the lubrication forces are relevant, especially for medium to high viscous fluids (in an unresolved CFD-DEM coupling approach). The cut-off distance in this case should be chosen such that the system doesn't produce instabilities. The decrease in cut-off distance requires a smaller time-step to avoid the scenarios where the particles establish

contacts before the lubrication force is cut-off. For viscous fluids, the lubrication force (i.e., fluid viscosity) could be included in the calibration.

- For short grinding times with less beads, one may couple the (CFD-)DEM with PBM as a two-way coupling i.e., the simulations provide data to PBM while PBM evolves the PSD and provides the feed back to the simulations. Since the product particles considered in this study are virtual, only the viscosity and contact parameters in the simulations can be updated from the PBM feedback. The simulations with modified parameters should then reach steady state, only when further coupling with PBM is possible. Such, two-way coupling of (CFD-)DEM with PBM worsens the simulation time, which is not desirable in process up-scaling. PBM on its own can yield results in a few minutes. Therefore, it is favourable to de-couple the (CFD-)DEM and PBM, but understand the system dynamics using (CFD-)DEM and then utilize the system dynamics in PBM.
- Material breakage characterization is an important aspect to realize the breakage rates and breakage distributions in PBM. The characteristics of material breakage threshold and progeny distribution (with respect to an applied energy), should be identified either experimentally or with back-calculation techniques.
- PBM of wet stirred media milling requires the total mass captured for each particle class i.e., the mass captured is available for breakage. It could be assumed that (at least) one product particle is available for each collision, which is valid for certain solids concentration range and particle sizes. However, a true description of the captured mass should be known either experimentally or with a simulation approach.

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